

FunGlass School 2018 / part 1

Book of Abstracts

ČERTOV, May 16- 18, 2018

ORGANIZING INSTITUTIONS:

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Čertov, May 16- 18, 2018

SCIENTIFIC BOARD: Dušan Galusek, Prof., DSc., Marek Liška, Prof., DSc.

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FunGlass
centre for functional and
surface functionalized glass

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BIOMATERIALS

Preparation of Bioglass for 3D scaffolds

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ABSTRACT

The presented work describes the first step in a project focused on the preparation of three-dimensional (3D) bioglass scaffolds for the second most commonly transplanted tissue worldwide in the human body, which is bone. Preparation of the bioglass 45S5 powder and doping it with the selected therapeutic inorganic ions was the first step. Optimisation of the preparation and characterization of the resulted powders via SEM, EDX, XRD and DSC was carried out. Prepared powders will be utilized for the 3D scaffolds via the tape casting technique followed by stacking and sintering. The main goal is to prepare material with enhanced mechanical properties (isotropic or anisotropic) and with enhanced ion release.

The field of bioactive materials started Hench et al. in 1971 with the discovery of 45S5 bioglass [1]. It is a special composition of silicate glass containing, 45 % SiO₂, 24.5 % CaO, 24.5 % Na₂O and 6 % phosphorus pentoxide P₂O₅ in wt.%. Bioactive glasses and glass-ceramics are a diverse group of materials possessing a unique set of physicochemical properties that make them useful for bone repair. Developing bioactive three-dimensional scaffolds to support bone regeneration has, therefore, become a key area of focus within bone tissue engineering. Such scaffolds are subjected to many requirements including biocompatibility, osteogenesis, biodegradability, and mechanical competence, all of which must be considered in the design features [2-4]. The microstructure of scaffolds plays also a major role in encouraging cell viability, tissue ingrowth and mechanical properties. The selected scaffold should replace the mechanical forces and therefore ideal scaffold would have a compressive strength comparable to cortical bone of 100 – 230 MPa (along the long axis) with Young`s modulus close to 7 – 30 GPa and tensile strength of > 150 MPa [5-7]. Such ideal values have to be achieved from materials containing porosities in the range from 60 – 90 % and an average pore size > 150 μm [8, 9]. Therefore, preparation of scaffolds favourable to cellular function, cellular viability and mechanical integrity remains still challenging task [10, 11].

The proposed work should lead to bioglass scaffolds with better mechanical properties as recent state of the art with similar or better bioactivity. The tape casting method followed by stacking, burn-out and sintering will be applied to obtain the desired 3D scaffold. However, in the first step the powder preparation procedure via the glass melting process was optimised on composition similar to 45S5 bioglass, in order to obtain material suitable for the above mentioned tape casting technique. Additionally, three different composition of doped 45S5 bioglass with 4 wt. % of therapeutic inorganic ions (TII) of zinc, strontium and boron, were prepared and characterised. Calculated compositions of the bioglass are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Theoretical compositions calculated for the bioglass composition in wt. %.

Name	SiO ₂	CaO	Na ₂ O	P ₂ O ₅	ZnO	SrO	B ₂ O ₃
45S5	45	24.5	24.5	6			
45S5+4Zn	44.5	21.5	24.2	5.93	4		
45S5+4Sr	44.5	21.5	24.2	5.93		4	
45S5+4B	44.5	21.5	24.2	5.93			4

Obtained bioglass was grained and sieved through 25 µm sieve. Characterisation of the prepared glasses and powders was done by SEM (EDX), XRD analysis and DSC measurement. Possible spheroidization of the grained powder 45S5 was performed via flame synthesis.

Successful preparation of the 45S5, in this first step, are going to be useful by guiding and set-up of the followed phases of the project e.g. by suspension preparation for tape casting, stacking and sintering process. The in vitro biological testing of the prepared 4 compositions via the indirect cytotoxicity in osteoblast cells is also ongoing. In vitro testing shall not only tell if the material is suitable from the biological point of view, but also should provide information about possible design stacking of the individual layers for 3D scaffold.

Keywords: bioglass, compositions analysis, glass melting,.

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Novel Bioglass-Polysaccharide Composites: Preparation of Mesoporous Glass Nanoparticles

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ABSTRACT

The study of interfacial bonding between inorganic particles (based on silica or glass) and polymeric medium is a challenge for improvement of structural compatibility of the glass-polymer composites such as chemical composition, microstructure and mechanical strength [1,2]. This approach can be realized using the preparation of nanoparticles bearing a well-defined surface and structural characteristics such as chemical composition, shape, size distribution, mesoporosity, specific surface area and agglomeration behaviour [3,4,5]. The second approach relates to the indirect determination of the physicochemical interactions between particles and polymers (such as e.g., electrostatic attractions) by means of characterization of the particle behaviour in polymeric solution such as Zeta potential, dissolution and corrosion rate, formation of polymeric film on the particle surface and so on [6]. Silica-based systems as a non-crystalline amorphous solids are the promising candidates for this purpose because of their relative easily chemical characterization, ability to form (nano)particles, sorption properties, chemical reactivity and durability after annealing (calcination), as well as due to their bioactivity and biocompatibility [7,8].

This contribution is focused on the preparation and characterization of silica nanoparticles (particularly in the glass form) which would be suitable as a fillers for composites containing modified chitin as a carbohydrate polymer matrix. For the synthesis, we used modified Stöber method in the presence of the basic catalyst (such as ammonia or NaOH) and hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide as a pore-forming agent. The formation of mesoporous nanoparticles should increase their specific surface area and thus the adhesive bonding with chitin polymer. Moreover, an addition of calcium precursors (such as e.g., calcium nitrate) to the suspension of particles after sol-gel process was carried out in order to incorporate calcium ions inside the silica structure. Based on the increase of calcium content in silica/glass particles, we would like to ensure the ionic interaction with phosphate groups of chemically-modified chitin and thus the overall integrity of this silica/glass-chitin composite. Moreover, the controllable release of calcium ions from the composite to the biological environment should ensure a therapeutic activity of this material in relation to the formation of hydroxyapatite as a building block of bone tissues.

Keywords: bioglass nanoparticles, mesoporosity, composite, bone regeneration

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SiO₂ nanoparticles, properties and interaction with amino acids

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ABSTRACT

This work deals with the determination of the influence of glycine on the properties of sols, which were stabilized by NaOH and NH₄OH solutions and their xerogels, which were prepared in “polymeric silicic acid (PSA) – water (H₂O) – sodium hydroxide (NaOH) – glycine (Gly)” system and “PSA – H₂O – ammonium hydroxide (NH₄OH) – Gly” system, respectively. Using acidic ion exchanger, the polymeric silicic acid sol, prepared from aqueous solution of sodium silicate (Na₂SiO₃), was stabilized in the first system by addition of NaOH solution and then, the resulting weight ratio of $w(\text{SiO}_2):w(\text{Na}_2\text{O})$ in sol was 150:1. In the second system, the given sol was stabilized by addition of NH₄OH solution and then, the resulting weight ratio of $w(\text{SiO}_2):w(\text{NH}_4\text{OH})$ in sol was 60:1. The stabilization of SiO₂ sols was completed by refluxing for 3 hours at the boiling point of the solvent in both systems. Nine sols with a different mole ratio of $x(\text{Gly}):x(\text{SiO}_2)$ in sol were prepared from the stabilized sols after 24 hours from their preparation. Their molar composition is shown in Tab. 1. These sols were prepared by the following way: the required amounts of water as well as the solution of glycine (10 wt. %) were added drop by drop into required amount of stabilized sol during stirring. The obtained mixture was stirred for 30 min. The xerogels were prepared 24 hours after preparation of sols by drying in a thin layer at 80 °C to constant weight. After drying, the xerogels were stored in an environment with RH = 43.2 %. Before Raman spectroscopy measurements, the xerogels were crushed to the fractions under 0.315 nm.

Table 1 Molar composition of sols

Sample designation	$x(\text{SiO}_2)$	$x(\text{Gly})$	$x(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	$x(\text{Gly}):x(\text{SiO}_2)$
Sol CB16/CD17				
002S	0.0061	0.0000	0.9939	0.0000
003S	0.0061	0.0004	0.9935	0.0667
004S	0.0061	0.0008	0.9931	0.1334
005S	0.0061	0.0012	0.9927	0.2001
006S	0.0061	0.0016	0.9923	0.2668
007S	0.0061	0.0020	0.9918	0.3335
008S	0.0061	0.0025	0.9914	0.4002
009S	0.0061	0.0029	0.9910	0.4669
010S	0.0061	0.0033	0.9906	0.5336

The particle size of sols was determined by dynamic light scattering (DLS) method. The result of DLS is a distribution of intensity according to diameter of particles. The distribution of intensity according to diameter of particles was converted by calculation to the distribution of volume according to diameter of particles. Next, the distribution of intensity according to diameter of particles was deconvoluted, using PeakFit 4.12 program, assuming the log-normal distribution of particle diameters to the particle groups. Each particle group was characterized by the estimation of the mean value (EMV) and the extent of particles dispersion (EPD) of particle diameter. From the cumulative curves of intensity according to particles diameter, the polydispersity index was determined for each group of particles. The specific

surface area and porosity of xerogels were determined, using nitrogen adsorption. The structure of xerogels was characterized by Raman spectroscopy. Raman spectra were measured by the Renishaw inVia Reflex Raman microspectrometer. The measurement conditions were following: center at 900 cm^{-1} , 3600 accumulations and exposure time of 10 seconds.

Fig. 1 The dependence of EMV on the ratio of $x(\text{Gly}):x(\text{SiO}_2)$ in sol for a) particles of the 1st group, b) particles of the 2nd group

Fig. 2 The dependence: a) of specific surface area, b) of pore volume on the ratio of $x(\text{Gly}):x(\text{SiO}_2)$ in sol

From particle size results it was found that the particles of the 1st group form the dominant volume fraction and only a negligible volume fraction is formed by the particles of the 2nd group in all sols. The EMV in both particle groups are significantly lower in the second system than in the first system (Fig.1). Fig. 1 also shows the fact that the increasing of the $x(\text{Gly}):x(\text{SiO}_2)$ ratio in sol leads to the increasing of the EMV of the first particle group as well as the second group of particles in the first system. Fig. 2 shows that both specific surface area and pore volume are lower for the xerogels prepared from the sols in the first system, and the increasing of the $x(\text{Gly}):x(\text{SiO}_2)$ ratio in sol is accompanied by a decreasing of their values. From the Raman spectra deconvolution results in the region of $300\text{-}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$, it was found that the increasing of the $x(\text{Gly}):x(\text{SiO}_2)$ ratio in sol is accompanied by the decreasing of the intensity of the 6-membered (6R) and 3-membered (3R) ring units in the first system and 5-membered (5R), 6R and double 4-membered (D4R) ring units in the second system. By the increasing of the $x(\text{Gly}):x(\text{SiO}_2)$ ratio in sol, the increasing of the intensity of the bending vibrations $\delta(\text{CCO})$, wagging vibrations $\omega(\text{COO})$ and bending vibrations $\delta(\text{NCC})$ is observed for both systems.

Keywords: aqueous SiO₂ sol, glycine, properties, stability, xerogels.

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Inorganic-organic materials prepared by sol-gel method

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ABSTRACT

The present paper describes the effect of the molar ratios $R = x(\text{H}_2\text{O})/(x(\text{TEOS})+x(\text{OTES})) = 2, 4, 6$ and $K = x(\text{OTES})/(x(\text{TEOS})+x(\text{OTES})) = 0, 0.125, 0.25, 0.375, 0.5$ on the surface properties of inorganic-organic layers and the effect of the heat treatment on the surface properties of non-corroded and corroded inorganic-organic layers prepared from sol with molar ratios $R = 6$ and $K = 0.3$. Each inorganic-organic layer was prepared in „triethoxy(octyl)silane (OTES) - tetraethoxysilane (TEOS) - water (H₂O) - isopropyl alcohol (IPA) - nitric acid (HNO₃)“ system. The content of silicon dioxide and nitric acid in sols was constant: $x(\text{OTES})+x(\text{TEOS}) = 0.05$ and $x(\text{HNO}_3) = 0.005$. Prepared inorganic-organic sols were applied by the dip-coating technique on cleaned glassy substrates 24 hours after sol preparation. The substrates were withdrawn from the sols at a speed of 60 mm.min⁻¹. The layers prepared from sols with R values from 2 to 6 and K values from 0 to 0.5 were heat treated at 140 °C for 2 hours and the layers prepared from sol with $R = 6, K = 0.3$ were heat treated at 140, 160, 180, 200 and 220 °C for 2 hours. The inorganic-organic layers prepared from sol with $R = 6, K = 0.3$ were corroded by distilled water and 5% NaCl for 5 hours. Surface properties such as hydrophobicity, surface free energy and its polar and dispersion components, morphology and topography (*rms*-roughness) were observed for each inorganic-organic layer. The contact angle of distilled water and diiodomethane on inorganic-organic layers was determined by the method of sitting drop. The mean values of contact angle of water were considered as a measure of the hydrophobicity. The Owens-Wendt method was used to calculate the surface free energy (SFE) and its dispersion and polar component. The morphology and topography (*rms*-roughness) were observed by the use of atomic force microscopy. For determination the “sol composition - layer surface properties” relation, the model selection approach, based on the corrected Akaike information criterion, was used for the determination the regression model. We found out, that the hydrophobicity, SFE, dispersion component of SFE, morphology and *rms*-roughness of inorganic-organic layers, prepared from sols with R values from 2 to 6 and K values from 0 to 0.5, depended on K as well as R molar ratios. These layers were hydrophobic, except for layers prepared from sols with R values from 2 to 6 and K values from 0 to 0.09, which were hydrophilic. Maximal values of hydrophobicity and *rms*-roughness, and minimal values of SFE and its dispersion component were observed near to values of mole ratios of $R = 6$ and $K = 0.325$. The polar component of SFE depended only on value of K mole ratio and its minimal values were reached for K values near to 0.325. Surfaces of inorganic-organic layers prepared from sols with R values from 2 to 4 and K values from 0 to 0.5 were practically smooth and consisted of uniformly distributed small grained formations. These grained formations were also observed on the surface of layer prepared from sol with molar ratios $R = 6$ and $K = 0$. The enhancement of molar ratio K in sols led to creating a rough surface with non-uniformly distributed elevations and relatively smooth places. Besides the quality description of observed properties, the mentioned approach allowed us the finding of the maximal value of hydrophobicity near to values of molar ratios of $R = 6$ and $K = 0.3$. We prepared layers for calculated R and K values and we found out, that water contact angle was 112.6°. This was in very good agreement with calculated value of contact angle, which was 112.4°. This finding led us to question how the heat treatment of layers prepared from sol with molar ratios of $R = 6$ and $K = 0.3$ would affect the surface properties of layers before and during corrosion.

We found out, that the observed surface properties of non-corroded and corroded inorganic-organic layers, prepared from sol with molar ratios of $R = 6$ and $K = 0.3$, depend on the temperature of heat

treatment. The prepared non-corroded layers were hydrophobic. Inorganic-organic layers corroded by distilled water and 5% NaCl were hydrophobic up to a temperature of 180 °C and above this temperature, the layers became hydrophilic. Surface free energy and its components of non-corroded and corroded layers slightly increased with increasing temperature of heat treatment. Surfaces of non-corroded and corroded layers consisted of non-uniformly distributed spherical bumps and depressions of different size and shape. The spherical bumps reduced their size with increasing temperature of heat treatment. *Rms*-roughness of non-corroded and corroded layers decreased with increasing temperature of heat treatment.

Keywords: corrosion, hydrophobicity, inorganic-organic layers, morphology, surface free energy, topography

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The influence of glass cleaning process on surface properties

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ABSTRACT

Before the deposition or application of the layers, the step of the substrate cleaning is very important. The bad cleaned substrate has a negative influence on the quality of the resulting layer. For this reason, this paper deals with different ways of glass cleaning and the influence on its surface properties. For this purpose, we chose 6 glass cleaning procedures (SA–SF). The cleaning procedures are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 : Process of glass cleaning – system SA-SF

The quality of the cleaning was assessed by contact angle, surface free energy, rms-roughness, morphology and topography. The contact angle of water and diiodmethane on the surface of the samples was determined by the method of the sessile drops. The values of the contact angle on the surface with the standard deviations are shown in Table 1. The surface free energy (SFE), and its polar and dispersive components were calculated, using the Owens – Wendt method (Tab. 1). The values of SFE and its components are not changed significantly with the glass cleaning process.

Using the Innova atomic force microscope (Bruker) in tapping mode, the surface of the glasses was evaluated for all the procedures, which are shown in the Fig. 1. The measurement was

carried out at room temperature. We measured 5 randomly selected areas for each one sample. Data from atomic force microscope were evaluated in NanoScope Analysis 1.5. The same program was used for calculation of the rms-roughness (Tab. 1). The most abrasive surface was observed for the sample, which was cleaned by the procedure designated as SC.

Tab. 1 : Contact angle, surface free energy, rms-roughness

	Contact angle (°)		Surface free energy (mJ/m ²)			rms-roughness (nm)
	distilled water	diiodmethane	SFE	Sp	Sd	
SA	39.63 ± 0.47	46.81 ± 0.23	62.02	25.99	36.03	2.61
SB	42.12 ± 0.33	50.46 ± 0.22	59.66	25.65	34.01	3.18
SC	42.07 ± 0.46	43.90 ± 0.34	61.33	23.74	37.59	10.87
SD	48.95 ± 0.19	43.34 ± 0.26	57.43	19.54	37.89	4.46
SE	32.11 ± 0.79	43.79 ± 0.26	66.84	29.18	37.66	5.54
SF	34.62 ± 1.37	45.04 ± 0.27	65.28	28.20	37.08	2.82
Sp = polar component SFE, Sd = dispersion component SFE						

Based on the above results, the SA procedure is the most suitable for surface modification. The given procedure of cleaning had the lowest damaging influence on the glass surface and it is important to point out that this procedure is the simplest in comparison with the other used procedures. Therefore we are going to use it in the future experiments.

Keywords: AFM, cleaning process, contact angle, rms-roughness, surface free energy.

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Preparation and characterization of novel borate bioactive glass composition – characterization and corrosion behaviour

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ABSTRACT

The era of tissue engineering in 21st century came to its third phase – we no longer want to introduce artificial materials, which retain their properties thanks to their inertness and everlasting durability against the harsh bodily conditions. Instead, our intent is to induce self-regeneration of tissues, which do not heal themselves under normal conditions.

Thus, the use of bioactive materials arose, with a very challenging task: to heal the wounded tissue and to accelerate the healing rates without the use of hormone-based drugs.

There are two main approaches to bioactive materials:

a) creation of a bond between the artificial tissue and body part through chemical reactions between material surface and cell expression products, and

b) the growth of the original tissue via artificial material decomposition and subsequent transformation of the dissolution products by tissue-generating cells.

Both ways are plausible for the medical application of the bioactive materials, but only the second option offers one additional property: retaining the original mechanical properties. The balance is often hard to reach for artificial joint or bone implants, since they are manufactured from hard and very durable alloys, which do not offer natural flexibility and torsion resistance. The mechanical stress created at the contact points is often the point of failure.

Retaining the original mechanical properties is one of the main challenges in the field of tissue engineering (TE). Maintaining the perfect balance between the material dissolution and tissue regeneration, so either the implant does not disappear before the tissue is fully reconstructed, or to avoid local inflammation, due to the implant material dissolution being too slow.

Dissolution of glass matrix takes place through a sequence of chemical reactions [1, 2]. Simply put, the bridging bonds slowly ‘open’, releasing the molecules of glass components, changing the surrounding pH, which alter the reaction kinetics. The glass surface produces a lot of material to be taken care of – either by flushing away into the solution, or by recrystallization of secondary phases on top of ‘corrosion’ layers. These crystalline phases are useful in the recreation of bone tissue, since one of the main bone constituents is hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3\text{OH}$).

Bioactive properties of certain glass compositions have been proposed since Larry Hench discovered the signature 45S5 Bioglass[®][3]. He proposed that some ionic products of glass dissolution could increase healing rate inside the human body [4]. The main disadvantage of the 45S5 Bioglass[®] was its SiO_2 matrix. Although soluble, the glass endures the corrosion for periods longer than 30 days [5, 6]. The dissolution rate has been successfully reduced by adjusting the composition and the shape of the resulting material (e.g. fibers, microspheres [7]). Modified bioactive silicate glasses (13-93, 45S5) inevitably led to conclusion, that not only silicate matrix, but also borate or phosphate glass network produces hydroxyapatite under corrosive conditions of either deionised water or simulated body fluid [8-10].

This paper focuses on preparation and development of a potentially bioactive glass

compositions, containing B_2O_3 , either as a main glass network creating oxide (borate glass) or a modifier (borosilicate glass).

Two samples of boron-containing glass have been prepared: 13-93B1 borosilicate glass ($34SiO_2$ $19B_2O_3$ $20CaO$ $12K_2O$ $5MgO$ $6Na_2O$ $4P_2O_5$ wt%) and 13-93B3 borate glass ($53B_2O_3$ $20CaO$ $12K_2O$ $5MgO$ $6Na_2O$ $4P_2O_5$ wt%). These boron-containing glasses will be compared to a silicate bioactive glass 45S5 ($45SiO_2$ $24.5CaO$ $24.5Na_2O$ $6P_2O_5$ wt%). Conventional melt-quenching method (High-temperature furnace Classic 0718E) was utilized to melt the glass at $1100^\circ C$ and $1200^\circ C$ (13-93B1, 13-93B3, respectively.) Bulk glass was pulverized and sieved to $25\mu m$ particle size fraction for further use.

For characterization approach, SEM (JEOL JSM 7600) was used to observe the bulk glass surface, and EDS semi-quantitative analysis was used to partially determine the glass composition. XRD (Panalytical Empyrean) was utilized to determine the vitreous character of the material matrix. TG and DSC (Netzsch STA 449 F1) analysis was used to determine T_g and melting point of the glass materials.

Density of the prepared glass was determined via two methods: pycnometric weighing in acetone and by using a helium pycnometer (Quantachrome Ultrapyc 1200e). Determination of glass density is an important parameter to assess surface/volume ratio for subsequent corrosion assays. Furthermore, the samples were decomposed in microwave digestion system (Berghof Speedwave 4) for ICP-OES (Agilent 5100) analysis.

The future task is to perform static corrosion test in deionized water at three temperatures: 37, 40 and $60^\circ C$. Subsequent analysis of the dissolution products as well as sample surface analysis will be performed to determine the corrosion rate and potential bioactivity in terms of ionic amount transferred into the solution as well as forming of the crystalline phases. After that, corrosion test in simulated body fluid (saturated ionic solution) will be performed to approximate for the bodily conditions. Besides, chemical analysis in solid-state will be performed via XRF (Bruker S8 Tiger)

Successful characterization of borate-based bioactive glass will provide data needed to subsequently prepare a novel glass composition, doped with additional therapeutic ions, such as Zn, Sr or even Ce, Ga and Nb. The corrosion rate of the resulting material could be modified by changing the powder properties, e.g. by fabrication of microspheres with different corrosion rate, which could be mixed with the sieved glass powder to achieve certain corrosion rate. The outlook for the material application will be fabrication of 3-D scaffolds via foam-replication method and to measure mechanical properties of such scaffold, as well as determination of mechanical properties.

Keywords: bioactive glass, silicate glass, borate glass, characterization, corrosion

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Magnetic Mesoporous Silica microspheres- Synthesis and Biomedical Application

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the synthesis of magnetic nanostructures has become a particularly important research field due to their advantages, such as magnetic properties, chemical stability, and biocompatibility. Magnetic nanocrystals have been intensively studied not only for fundamental scientific interest but also potential applications in biomedical fields, especially in the field of targeted drug delivery. Magnetic nanoparticle-based targeting can reduce or eliminate the side effects of conventional chemotherapy by the systematic distribution of drugs and lower doses of cytotoxic compounds. The magnetic nanostructures used for drug delivery systems are usually iron oxides (Fe_3O_4 , Fe_2O_3 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$). The magnetic nanoparticles can be used for the purpose of targeted drug delivery because they can be remotely navigated to the intended side via application of an external magnetic field gradient. The modification or coating of magnetic nanoparticles with silica or polymers has been extensively studied for targeted drug delivery. Mesoporous silica is a promising and appropriate matrix for magnetic core-shell particles or nanocomposites, because this material has a low toxicity, very high and easily functionalisable specific surface area, large pore volume and tunable pore diameter in addition to being biocompatible. The core-shell and nanocomposite magnetic spheres which combine the advantages of mesoporous silica and magnetic carrier technology are very much appealing in targeted drug delivery. However, the drug storage capacities of these materials are relatively low due to limited pore volume. Recently published articles¹⁻³ revealed that hollow mesoporous silica spheres with a large hollow space and ordered 3D pore network shell could store significantly more drug molecules and take part in the sustained release of drugs than conventional mesoporous materials such as MCM-41, MCM-48 and SBA-15.

Drug-delivery systems based on mesoporous magnetic materials have been widely synthesized and investigated for different chemotherapeutic drug loading and their interactions with the tumour cells⁴⁻⁵. Core-shell mesoporous magnetic nanocomposite particles with irregular morphology and a wide particle size distribution, from hundreds of nanometers to several micrometers in sizes were synthesized by coating a mesoporous layer onto monodisperse magnetite nanocrystals⁶. Magnetic micro particles generated in the porous matrix such as MCM-41 and MCM-48 mesoporous spheres have been reported⁷. Silica coated iron nanoparticles were also prepared by a gas phase based method⁸. These magnetic silica nanocomposites exhibited strong magnetism. Surfactant assisted encapsulation of magnetic nanoparticles into the mesoporous silica to prepare magnetic silica nanocomposites were also reported⁹. Biodegradable copolymer coated magnetic mesoporous spheres were also synthesized¹⁰ and modified for the release rate of a drug by a simple hydrothermal treatment¹¹. Recent research activities are more focused on the synthesis of functionalized silica based magnetic nano carriers for better targeting. The aim of our work is to synthesize magnetically driven surface functionalised hollow silica core shell microspheres for delivery of drugs and therapeutic agents. The magnetite core synthesised by solvothermal method are yield more monodisperse particles than the other methods used for synthesis of magnetic nanocrystals. Folate-receptor mediated mesoporous outer silica surface are beneficial for a better cellular uptake and increased release rate of drugs. The hollow space in between the core and shell of the microspheres could be generated by templating method using selective polymers and surfactants as sacrificial materials. Chemically modified hollow inner surface of these core shell microspheres can store more drugs than conventional core shell microspheres. Therefore, surface

functionalised receptor mediated magnetic hollow submicron sized core shell mesoporous silica spheres can be thus considered as promising carriers for drug delivery.

Keywords: Drug Delivery, Magnetic, Mesoporous, Nanoparticles, Silica.

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Mesoporous Glass Nanospheres for Selective Targeting of Cancer Cells

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ABSTRACT

MCM-41 Ordered mesoporous silica first discovered at 1992 [1], and proposed as a drug delivery system at 2001 [2]. Since than silica based glass microspheres, such as MCM-41, SBA-15 or MCM-48 type ordered mesoporous glass materials have been consider as an ideal material for incorporation of drugs, genes and other therapeutic agent carriers and control release systems.

Drug delivery system is a promising route for localized cancer treatment. It can control the rate and period of the drug delivery at targeted, diseased site of the body. The incorporation of this substance and zero-release before getting targeted area can be achieved by surface modification of the bioactive glass particles to include functional groups that will allow the anchorage of certain therapeutic molecules, in processes that may be governed by external stimuli such as temperature, electric field, magnetic field, light, or internal stimuli such as, pH, redox potential, enzymes [3,4].

Figure 1. Preparation of Mesoporous Glass Nanoparticles

The aim of this preliminary study is the preparation of mesoporous glass particles with spherical shape, monodispersed size and low agglomeration. For this purpose, we used modified Stöber method from tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) in the presence of hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) as a surfactant, which template the TEOS during sol-gel synthesis. And NaOH was used as a catalyst in aqueous environment. The final ratio of reaction mixture was TEOS: NaOH: H₂O: CTAB = 1.00: 0.29: 1124.16: 0.11 mol. The TEOS added the system dropwise and the whole system was kept in 80 °C for preventing the agglomeration during the synthesis. The white suspension obtained was magnetically stirred for further 2 h at 80 °C. Then the suspension was filtrated and washed 3x with H₂O and 96 % EtOH. Then, the white powder was dried under vacuum for 1 h. After drying, the powder was washed with 96% EtOH (50 ml, 70 °C, 15 min, 500 rpm) in 250 ml glass flask and filtrated and washed again with absolute EtOH to remove residual water and salts from the particle surface. Than the particles were dried again overnight at 60 °C (40 °C for 0.5 ml/min) and calcinated at 650 °C (3 h, rate of heating: 1 °C/min) in order to remove surfactant from the glass particles.

Figure 2: SEM of before and after of calcination, silica xerogel (left) and silicate glass (right) prepared in the presence of NaOH and CTAB (2 h, 0.35 ml/min)

In conclusion, we successfully obtain silica and glass particles with spherical shape, size about below 200 nm and the low agglomeration behaviour as can be seen in figure 2. Under the dropping rate in an interval 0.35 ml/min, the obtained morphology was similar with the morphology of silica particles obtained via original Stöber method. At the same time, calcination of particles did not affect the particle morphology. On the other hand, the successful removing of CTAB as a surfactant from the silica particles via calcination using Raman and thermogravimetry was confirmed. Nevertheless, the mesoporosity of particles (which is also expected based on the using of surfactant during the sol-gel process) should be confirmed by the measurement of the specific surface area.

Keywords: Drug delivery, MCM-41, Mesoporus silica.

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CORROSION / WEATHERING

Effect of Gamma Radiation on the Chemical Durability of Glass Fibrous Insulation Used in Nuclear Power Plants

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ABSTRACT

The glass fibers play a significant role regarding the security system of the nuclear plants. Glass fibers are mainly used as thermal and electrical insulation. In nuclear power plants the glass fibrous insulations NUKON, BOURRE or IZOMER TT are commonly used. In case of Loss Of Coolant Accident (LOCA) the insulation is mechanically destroyed by steam impact and stored in the bottom part of the reactor containment immersed in the alkaline coolant liquid. As far as the commercially produced thermal fiber insulations are not alkali resistant the glass dissolution and later the back precipitation from the over saturated solutions take place. A part of the fibers is also captured on the sump screen and thus preventing the recirculation of the coolant in the emergency cooling system. As the partially dissolved fibers can be mechanically destroyed (crushed) the blocking of the strainer can achieve such level that the emergency cooling system fails. In this situation the high head loss reaches the value disabling the operation of pumps. The above effect of strainer blocking can be dramatically enhanced by tightening of the fiber bed by the back precipitated matter. It is well known that water solution in contact with a glass causes changes resulting in the structure transformation of glass surface, dissolution of a glass itself and formation of new glass surface layer. Therefore both the study of the kinetics and thermodynamics of the glass dissolution on one side and the monitoring of the hydrodynamic conditions, namely the time dependence of the head loss, is needed for correct modeling of the process and its consequences on the operability of the emergency systems. The chemical durability of gamma-irradiated glass fibrous insulation commonly used in the reactor containment of nuclear power plants was tested by static leaching tests at 70, 80 and 90°C. Distilled water was used as corrosive medium. Two radiation doses, 2 and 4 MGy, were applied, the higher one roughly corresponding to 30 years of irradiation in reactor containment. The glass insulation was irradiated at low (70°C) and increased (450°C) temperatures. The results of the static leaching tests were compared with those obtained for non-irradiated native glass fibers. Therefore, the aim of the present work is the study of influence of gamma irradiation and temperature on the chemical durability of glass fibers. This will be quantified by static leaching tests of non-irradiated native glass fibers and irradiated glass fibers performed in distilled water. The detailed analysis of results of static and flow thorough leaching tests leads to the hypothesis of quasi congruent glass dissolution. Using this assumption the leaching kinetics was described by the Aagaard Helgeson equation. The kinetic parameters were obtained by the non-linear regression analysis of time evolution of leaching solution composition.

Keywords: Glass fibers, gamma radiation, LOCA, chemical durability, corrosion, static leaching tests.

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Structure and properties of glass fibers insulation used in nuclear power plants

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ABSTRACT

The basic physical properties and chemical durability of glass used for production of the NUKON glass fibrous insulation were measured. This type of glass insulation is used in nuclear power plants and its properties are important for safety reasons – namely in the case of Loss Of Coolant Accidents (LOCA). During this postulated accident, the insulation can be damaged by the jet impact and carried to the screens of the emergency systems needed to cool the reactor. In this case, the fibers can be strongly corroded by particular coolant solutions and their behavior under this environment can modify the head loss of the screens. In addition corrosion products formed during contact of insulation fibers with aggressive cooling solution can cause changes, resulting in insufficient even functionless operation of the cooling system. Therefore the chemical durability of NUKON glass fibers was tested in present work by leaching corrosion tests. The coolant solution $H_3BO_3/Na_2B_4O_7$ was used as corrosive medium. The glass dissolution was followed by atomic emission spectrometry with inductively coupled plasma (ICP - OES). The low temperature viscosity was measured by the thermomechanical analysis. The temperature dependence of viscosity was described by the Andrade viscosity equation. The glass transition temperature and the thermal expansion coefficients of glass and metastable melt were determined by the thermodilatometry. The liquidus temperature was measured in the gradient furnace by the method of the first crystal. The glass density at laboratory temperature was measured by Archimedes method. The heat capacity and glass transition characteristic were determined by DSC method.

Keywords: Glass fibers insulation, LOCA, corrosion, nuclear power plants, physical properties, .

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Raman spectroscopic study of heavy weathered glass surface

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ABSTRACT

Glass is generally a stable and resistant material, but when in contact with either liquid or vapor water it is vulnerable to damage. The degradation of a glass surface due to interaction with the atmosphere is referred to as "weathering". Temperature and humidity cycling or storing glass in a wet confined space as well as increased concentration of aggressive gasses such as SO_x, CO₂, and NO_x usually promote weathering [1].

The chemical composition of a glass surface is a key factor in its interaction with the environment. Under certain exposure conditions its optical properties, chemistry and structure are modified by different weathering processes [2]. As a consequence of the interaction between the glass and a solution, irreversible changes in glass can be observed. Most important of them are as follows: dissolution of the glass, transfer of glass components into the solution, changes of glass surface composition, especially the depletion of alkali and alkali earth ions, and creation of secondary precipitated layers on the glass surface [3-4].

The barium crystal glass produced by RONA glassworks was used in this study. Glass samples of barium crystal glass were weathered at real conditions (not controlled conditions) (Figure 1) during the overseas transport to Malaysia and subsequently back to Slovakia. After that the storage for 3 months followed. Optical microscopy of the unweathered and weathered samples was carried out for visually characterization of the surface. Optical microscope observations were undertaken with Nikon LV UDM 100 with a 5 MPx CCD camera using the lens with 10x magnification. Obtained digital images were evaluated by NIS Elements ver. 3.4 software. On the weathered glass surface the high number of corrosion products of approximate size of (5 - 10) μm. Simultaneously big corrosion products with the size of (100-150) μm were found (Figures 2, 3). On the unweathered (native) glass surfaces only small non-homogeneities were observed.

The micro Raman spectroscopy was used for study of corrosion products observed by the optical microscopy. Raman spectra were recorded in the range of (300–1300) cm⁻¹ by RENISHAW inVia Reflex Raman spectrometer with the Leica DM2500 microscope. A 532 nm laser with 28.5 mW power was used as the excitation source for a spot of about 1 mm diameter. Only locations with significant corrosion were analyzed. The stoichiometric corrosion products can be identified by Raman spectroscopy by application of the proper spectral database (Figure 4).

It can be summarized that optical microscopy provided the basic information for identification of the morphology of the weathered glass surface. Four corrosion products (Euclase (Be-aluminosilicate (BeAlSiO(4)OH), Barium Carbonate (BaCO₃), Magnesium pyrophosphate (Mg₂P₂O₇·3H₂O) and Magnesium Nitrate (Mg(NO₃)₂·6H₂O) were identified by the micro Raman spectroscopy on the weathered glass surface by the S. T. Japan Spectral database.

Keywords: Barium crystal glass, optical microscopy, micro Raman spectroscopy, corrosion products

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Corrosion and low temperature degradation of zirconia – based dental ceramics

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ABSTRACT

Zirconium oxides stabilized in their tetragonal form by addition of yttria are suitable materials for various applications, including dental materials for implants or crowns. One of the advantages of this material is its non-metallic nature, which is important for patients allergic to metals, including titanium [1]. Zirconia ceramics are also characteristic by their good mechanical properties and biocompatibility. These good mechanical properties, especially fracture toughness and strength, are the consequence of phase transformation toughening, which increases its cracks propagation resistance [2]. However, zirconia ceramics is vulnerable to phenomenon known as aging or low temperature degradation (LTD) [1,3].

The overall aim of this work was the study of corrosion of a commercial 3Y-TZP dental ceramics and a Ce-TZP based nano-composite in aqueous media, evaluation of its influence on ion leaching, phase composition, mechanical properties and LTD under the conditions of accelerating ageing test (AAT) and, ultimately, to determine whether corrosion in acidic media is controlled by the same mechanism as LTD. Three different materials were tested: two commercial zirconia-based dental materials stabilized in their tetragonal form by addition of yttrium (3Y-TZP) – IVOCLAR IPS e.max® ZirCAD and DOCERAM Nacera®, and a Ce-TZP based nano-composite (denoted as LONGLIFE) prepared at INSA Lyon, France. All three ceramics have been corroded at three different temperatures (37, 60, 80 °C) in 4 % acetic acid as the corrosion medium for up to 31 days. Phase composition was determined by X-ray diffraction (Panalytical Empyrean powder diffractometer, CuK α radiation, in the 2 Θ range 25 – 75°). To monitor the amount of leached ions from the materials during the corrosion process chemical analysis of corrosion media was carried out by ICP – OES (Agilent Technologies 5100). The corrosion tests at 37°C were extended up to 265 days and for 60°C up to 130 days. Un-corroded materials were subjected also to accelerating aging test (AAT) and exposed to water vapour at an elevated temperature of 134 °C (one hour at 134 °C corresponds to 2 years at 37 °C [1]) up to 30 h. Before and after the exposure to AAT the content of monoclinic phase was determined, using X-ray diffraction. For comparison, AAT in acetic acid for the IVOCLAR dental ceramic is in progress. AAT in T= 134°C in water vapour have shown that commercial dental ceramics IVOCLAR was the material least resistant to LTD. The ICP-OES measurements were carried out to evaluate the influence of corrosion in 4 % acetic acid on ion leaching from zirconium dental ceramic and to prove that acidic corrosion of 3Y-TZP dental ceramics is associated with leaching of stabilizing ions from zirconia ceramics. Leaching of yttrium ions was observed from both tested yttria-stabilized zirconia dental ceramics IVOCLAR and DOCERAM. However, concentration of leached yttrium ions from IVOCLAR at T=37°C after 265 days of the experiment is almost 10 times higher than in DOCERAM (Fig. 1a). In the case of LONGLIFE the leaching of cerium ions was observed (Fig. 1a). In Y stabilized ceramics, the monoclinic phase appeared already before the corrosion and its content was slightly higher in DOCERAM (fig. 1b). However, after 265 days of corrosion the content of monoclinic phase in DOCERAM remains at a comparatively unchanged level. The effect of corrosion (Fig. 1. c) could be partial destabilization of tetragonal zirconia and an increase of the content of monoclinic phase observed e.g. at the surface of IVOCLAR after 130 days at T = 60 °C (Fig 1. d).

Fig 1. a) The amount of leached ions from dental ceramics at T = 37°C, b) Content of monoclinic phase after static test at 37 °C, c) The amount of leached ions from the dental ceramic materials at T = 60°C, d) Content of monoclinic phase after static test at 60 °C.

Conclusions

Acidic corrosion of 3Y-TZP dental ceramics at temperatures higher than 37°C is associated with leaching of yttrium ions from zirconia ceramics, resulting in partial destabilization of tetragonal zirconia and measurable increase of the content of monoclinic phase at the surface. So far, the experiment has shown that IVOCLAR is the material least resistant against corrosion and LTD. To confirm that the acidic environment accelerate corrosion mechanism and that corrosion is different process than LTD, the AAT in acetic acid 4% and T = 134 °C up to t = 30 h is in progress.

Keywords: corrosion, low temperature degradation, dental implants, acetic acid, accelerated aging test.

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Preparation and characterization of precursor derived ceramic coatings with glass filler particles on steel substrates

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ABSTRACT

A novel environmental barrier coating system for steel consisting of a perhydropolysilazane (PHPS) bond coat and a polysilazane-based glass/ceramic composite top coat has been developed. Glass powders were added as filler materials in order to densify and seal the coatings at the temperatures of their application, to increase the coating thickness and to improve its adhesion to substrate. Parameters like the type of precursor, the filler and glass systems, the volume fraction of the components and pyrolysis conditions were varied to optimize the composite coating system. After stabilizing the coating slurries, double layers consisting of a bond coat applied by dip coating and a top coat deposited by spray coating were prepared on stainless steel (AISI 441) substrates. The top coat was prepared by mixing defined volume fractions of a liquid polysilazane HTT1800, ceramic filler particles (yttria-stabilized zirconia - YSZ) and commercial barium silicate (G018-311, G018-385, Schott AG) and borosilicate (G8470, Schott AG) filler glass particles, which have similar thermal expansion coefficients ($9\text{-}10 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$) to that of the steel substrates ($14.5 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$). This mixture of glass filler particles was incorporated into the suspension using dispersing agents. In some cases, glass particles in the form of microspheres ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$) prepared by flame synthesis or a polycrystalline powder precursor ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$) for the preparation of glass microspheres were added as further passive fillers to the coatings. All coated samples were heat treated in air at the temperature of 750 °C for 1 h. Selected compositions of prepared composite coatings are shown in Tab. 1. The SEM/EDS examination of the coatings after pyrolysis was conducted with the use of a FEG SEM JEOL 7600f and was focused at evaluation of homogeneity, adhesion and possible failures of the coatings.

Tab. 1: The compositions of the composite top coats

COATING	COMPOSITION (vol. %) (after pyrolysis)					
	YSZ	$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$	G018-385	G018-311	G8470	HTT1800
C1	33	-	-	20	31	16
C2	37	9 (glass microspheres)	-	17	17	20
C3	30	21 (powder precursor)	16	13	-	20

In a Fig. 1a, a SEM micrograph of a HTT1800/glass composite coating (composition C1) after pyrolysis in air at the temperature of 750°C is presented. SEM micrograph of the cross-section shows that the coating exhibits significant fraction of large closed pores with a diameter up to 40µm, formed due to release of gases (such as CH_4 , NH_3 , H_2) generated during the polymer-to-ceramic transformation. The occurrence of such a blowing effect is caused by the trapping of the gaseous pyrolysis products due to the high amount of glass particles. The gas bubbles pulled the particles away from each other in order to create an escape path, causing coating expansion, especially at the pyrolysis temperature higher than

the softening point of the used glass fillers. Since diameter of the pores lies in the range of the coating thickness, such coating do not possess environmental barrier properties.

To reduce the porosity and the pore size of the coatings, polycrystalline powder precursor for preparation of glass microspheres ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$) or glass microspheres were used as additional passive fillers. These formed a rigid skeletal structure in the coating, thus facilitating escape of gases during pyrolytic conversion of the organosilicon precursor. In the case of the coating C2 (which includes glass microspheres), the pore size was reduced to $10\mu\text{m}$ after pyrolysis in air at 750°C . However, the high volume shrinkage of the polysilazane precursor led to formation of severe cracks distributed across the whole surface, which penetrate through the coating to the metal surface, as obvious from the cross section (Fig. 1b). Moreover, coating with a thickness of approximately $50\mu\text{m}$ delaminates from the steel substrate.

The composite coating (composition C3) provides the most promising overall results. The optimised composite top coating was prepared with YSZ, and powder precursors ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$) as passive filler and the glass systems G018-311 and G018-385 as sealing agents. On the basis of the analyzed surface and cross sectional micrographs (Fig. 1c), it can be concluded that the addition of powder precursor was effective at preventing the formation of cracks and pores. Furthermore, a homogenous distribution of the fillers particles (YSZ, powder precursor) within the polymer derived ceramic matrix is observed. After a thermal treatment in air at 750°C , the resultant coating with the thickness up to $90\mu\text{m}$ is almost fully dense, with no cracking or delamination and it is expected to prevent the access of aggressive environment to the steel substrate at temperatures up to 950°C .

Fig. 1: Cross-sectional SEM images after pyrolysis in air at 750°C : a) coating C1, b) coating C2, c) coating C3

Keywords: environmental barrier coating, passive filler, polymer-derived ceramics,

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Oxidation tests of steel AISI 441 and PDC coating with glass fillers for high temperature protection of metals

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the oxidation behaviour of ferritic steel grade AISI 441 and PDC coating is under investigation. The selected samples of composite layers (C2, C3) were further tested for their oxidative resistance in hot corrosive gases at temperatures up to 1000 °C. The pyrolysis of ceramic coatings carried out in the air (Nabertherm® N41 / H, Nabertherm, Germany) at the temperature 800 °C with a heating and cooling rate of 3 K / min for 1 hour. The purpose of the oxidation tests is a detailed microstructural analysis of the oxide layer formed on samples in a synthetic air atmosphere at different temperatures and exposure times, as non-coated steel (AISI 441) as a reference material as well as steel with selected types of coatings. High temperature oxidation tests were carried out in a high temperature horizontal electric tube furnace (Clasic 0213T, Clasic, Praha, Czech Republic) at the temperatures of 900 °C, 950 °C and 1000 °C and the exposure times in the range of 1 – 48 hours in flowing atmosphere of synthetic air (purity 99.5%, Linde, Slovakia).

After oxidation tests, the heat treated samples were further examined by the XRD study to identify the various phase formation with respect to temperature and heat treatment duration formed during oxidation (Fig. 2a,b). The Fe, Cr₂O₃, TiO₂ and spinel (Mn,Cr)₃O₄ phases have been identified from RTG records of steel substrates (Fig. 2a). In the case of coated samples (Fig. 2b), the dominant phases in initial stages of oxidation are the monoclinic and tetragonal ZrO₂. In the case of coating C2 and C3 (Fig. 2b), YAG crystallizes as the primary phase of the powdered precursor (AYZ20) which has been used as an additional filler. The crystallization of sealing glasses was observed. After longer periods of oxidation and higher oxidation temperatures, crystallization of ingested glass fillers leads to the formation of new crystalline phases (Ba(AlSiO₄)₂ - hexacelsian, celsian), but also to the formation of further phases (ZrSiO₄, YZr₃O₁₄) as a consequence of chemical reactions between the individual components layers. At 1000 °C (Fig. 2b) and after 24h oxidation, the presence of oxidation products (Mn, Cr)₃O₄ and Cr₂O₃ can also be observed, which means that due to the peeling of the protective layer, steel substrate with the atmosphere of air and its oxidation.

For a more detailed study of the oxidation products of stainless steel, SEM and EDS analysis (Fig. 3a,b) were used which demonstrated the presence of spinel (Mn,Cr)₃O₄ almost on the entire surface of the oxidized steel substrate (Fig. 3a). In addition to the spinel crystals, the rest of the surface of the steel substrate is covered with a thin layer of Cr₂O₃ and TiO₂, the thickness of the oxidation layer increasing with increasing time and temperature. The protective effect of PDC coatings was partially observed at 900 °C and 950 °C, while uncoated samples were already strongly oxidized at this temperature. After oxidation, both the weight gain and oxygen ingress into the stainless substrate are negligible. According to the visual inspection, coatings after the oxidation tests at temperatures of 900 and 950 °C appeared to be well adherent, did not peel off, no visible changes were observed on the surface. In consistent with the surface morphologies, numerous pores were found as well within the cross-section (Fig. 3b) of the as-prepared PDC glass ceramic coatings. The observed porosity is probably due to the non-effective removal of the gases entrapped in the sealant, during the longer heat treatment. In our glass-ceramic system, the particle boundaries are not evident and pores approach spherical shape (Fig. 3b), which indicates that residual porosity could be determined by bubble formation due to the release of dissolved

gas and insoluble gases (e.g. water vapour or air) entrapped in the initial pores. However, it can be seen from the SEM image (Fig. 3b) that at the temperature of 900 °C, due to the softening of the used glass fillers, the cracks in the layers gradually heal, indicating at least partial protection of the metal substrate. A self-sealing process likely occurred during the test, allowing the protection of the stainless steel against further oxidation. After longer exposure times also to progressive cracking and peeling of the layers and loss of oxidation resistance. Though these coatings are all successful in reducing oxygen ingress at high temperatures, they still face many challenges.

Fig. 2: XRD patterns of steel and coat C3 at the temperature 1000 °C and different times: a) steel, b) coat C3

Fig. 3: Microstructures of steel and C2 after oxidation tests a) steel 1000 °C/24h, b) C2 900 °C/24h

Keywords: polymer-derived ceramics, oxidation of steel and PDC coating

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STRUCTURE / PROPERTIES

Na₂O – CaO – MgO - SiO₂ glasses: selected physical properties and thermodynamic model

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ABSTRACT

Molar volume (V_m), thermal expansion (α), glass transition temperature (T_g), and molar refractivity (R_m) of $15\text{Na}_2\text{O}\cdot x\text{MgO}\cdot(10-x)\text{CaO}\cdot 75\text{SiO}_2$ glasses ($x = 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$) were measured [1]. The structure of studied glasses was described by the thermodynamic model of Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva [2-4]. From considered 27 components with the stoichiometry given by the composition of stable crystalline phases only eight were found in significant abundance in the studied glasses - namely: SiO_2 , $2\text{MgO}\cdot\text{SiO}_2$ (M2S), $\text{MgO}\cdot\text{SiO}_2$ (MS), $\text{Na}_2\text{O}\cdot 3\text{CaO}\cdot 6\text{SiO}_2$ (NC3S6), $\text{Na}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{CaO}\cdot 5\text{SiO}_2$ (NCS5), $\text{Na}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{MgO}\cdot 4\text{SiO}_2$ (NMS4), $\text{Na}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{SiO}_2$ (NS), and $\text{Na}_2\text{O}\cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$ (NS2). The mutual significant positive correlations were found between the equilibrium molar amounts of M2S vs MS, NMS4 vs NS, NCS5 vs NC3S6, and NS vs NS2. Thus only four significant uncorrelated components were considered in the multilinear regression analysis. The compositional dependence of the measured physical properties was described by multilinear dependences where the equilibrium molar amounts, n_i , of components with significant and uncorrelated abundance were taken as independent variables:

$$p(h) = \sum_i a_i n_i \quad (1)$$

The order of components considered in multilinear equation is: 1 – SiO_2 , 2-MS, 3 – NC3S6, 4 – NS2. Based on the statistical analysis, only the statistically significant components were retained in all obtained relationships [5]. It was proved, that the thermodynamic model describes the compositional dependence of studied physical properties with better accuracy than the model based on the glass compositions expressed by molar fractions of oxides. The obtained results are summarized in the following table.

Table 1: Results of multilinear regression analysis (Eq. 1), s_{apr} standard deviation of approximation, r correlation coefficient, F Fisher's F-statistic.

Property (p)						
Comp.	Value	$10^5 \cdot \alpha_g / \text{K}^{-1}$	$10^5 \cdot \alpha_m / \text{K}^{-1}$	T_g / K	$V_m / \text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$	$R_m / \text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$
SiO₂	a_1	7.5 ± 0.5	-	916 ± 314	18 ± 7	4.8 ± 0.8
MS	a_2	15.8 ± 1.5	-	-	41 ± 11	11.1 ± 2.5
NC3S6	a_3	-119.5 ± 3.0	29 ± 9	$5\,243 \pm 461$	216 ± 21	69.8 ± 4.9
NS2	a_4	22.4 ± 1.5	24 ± 1	$4\,440 \pm 868$	141 ± 11	43.2 ± 2.6
	s_{apr}	0.02	0.23	10	0.12	0.03
	r	1	1	1	1	1
	F	78 166	438	11 762	61 352	101 000

Figure 1: Experimental versus calculated R_m values obtained by multilinear regression analysis according to Eq. 1. Dashed lines represent the 95% confidence limit.

Keywords: glass, density, refractive index, glass transition, thermal expansion, thermodynamic model.

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Ion Exchange Strengthening of Thin Borosilicate Glass

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ABSTRACT

The weak and scattered strength of glass is the main drawback of using thin glasses in flexible electronics. Ion-exchange strengthening, which is also known as chemical strengthening, is an effective technique for improving the mechanical strength of thin glass.¹ Chemical strengthening is usually conducted by immersing a glass containing alkali ions, e.g. Na⁺, in a molten potassium nitrate bath for long time where larger potassium ions penetrate into the glass and partially take alkalis' sites. Sodium for potassium ion exchange is essentially an inter-diffusion process occurring between the glass surface and the molten salt; therefore, time and temperature are two influential factors that govern the ion-exchange process.^{2, 3, 4}

If the Na/K exchange occurs below the glass-transition temperature, “stuffing” larger potassium ions into the smaller alkali sites of glass produces compressive stress that can reinforce the surface flaws and improve the mechanical performance. The compressive stress depends on two competing processes: (1) stress build-up as a result of stuffing larger potassium ions and (2) stress relaxation due to viscous flow and structural relaxation.⁵ The magnitude of surface compression and its depth are two important factors determining the efficiency of chemical strengthening. While performing ion exchange at higher temperatures facilitates the replacement of ions and improves the potassium ions penetration depth, it accelerates stress relaxation accounting for the deterioration of surface compression. Although there are reports on impacts of structural relaxation on surface residual stress, there is no information about whether such changes can be used to modify the surface compression and improve the efficiency of chemical strengthening, particularly in case of thin glasses.⁶

Na-K ion exchange produces a glass whose molar volume is larger than the parent glass but smaller than a chemically equivalent as-melt one (CEAM). Consequently, during relaxation, the molar volume of glass surface increases towards the volume of CEAM; this produces additional compression in the glass surface.⁷ However, such a phenomenon is often disguised by rapid stress relaxation, and relaxation models following Burger's approach fail to distinguish between the stress relaxation and the structural relaxation. The stretched exponential model, which is proposed empirically by Kohlrausch in 1847, fits well the relaxation behaviour of disordered and quenched molecular systems; it allows us to investigate the relaxation phenomena in ion-exchanged glasses.⁸

In this study, thin borosilicate glass, D 263, supplied by Schott AG, was subjected to Na-K ion exchange in pure potassium nitrate salt kept at a temperature between 400 to 500 °C for 4h. Further heat treatments were carried out by immersing ion-exchanged samples for few minutes in a molten potassium nitrate bath to stimulate relaxation at elevated temperatures. The generated surface compressive stress and its depth were measured using a surface stress meter. The compressive stress case depth increases continuously by increasing the treatment temperature; while, the generated stress at the surface is deteriorated after a certain temperature. Vickers' indentations revealed that the damage resistance of glass increases significantly after ion-exchange; moreover, the flexural strength of glass is improved significantly by chemical strengthening. The results showed that subjecting to elevated temperatures causes stress relaxation in the glass and, consequently, the strength declines; conversely, a very short heat treatment at a temperature close to the glass-transition temperature improves the mechanical strength of ion-exchanged samples.

Using stretched exponential relaxation model revealed that while stress relaxation is responsible for stress degradation at low temperatures, the structural relaxation is dominant at temperatures close to the glass-transition temperature. The expansion of glass surface due to the structural relaxation is probably responsible for the increase in mechanical strength of samples subjected to an additional heat treatment. However, understanding the mechanics of increasing strength via relaxation is not straightforward and requires detailed analysis.

Further studies using Raman spectroscopy, NMR spectroscopy and diffraction methods are recommended to probe short and medium-range order in the ion-exchanged glass, and find the connection between the stress generation and hosting larger potassium ions in the glass structure.

Keywords: borosilicate glass, chemical strengthening, stress relaxation, structural relaxation

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Compositional dependence of surface tension of 15(Na₂O/K₂O)·10(CaO/ZnO)·75(ZrO₂/SiO₂) glass melts

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ABSTRACT

The surface tension of molten glass is of very high importance in glass production technology, especially during the fining process. On the other hand the compositional dependence of glass surface tension enables determination of surface active components. The drop (sessile or pendant) profile analysis is widely used to measure the surface tension of glass melts. The accuracy of surface tension measurement has been improved by applying the technologies of video-imaging digitization and best-fitting algorithms [1-4].

Surface tension of glass melts with as weighted composition $x\text{Na}_2\text{O}\cdot(15-x)\text{K}_2\text{O}\cdot y\text{CaO}\cdot(10-y)\text{ZnO}\cdot z\text{ZrO}_2\cdot(75-z)\text{SiO}_2$ ($x = 0, 15$; $y = 0, 10$; $z = 0, 1, 3, 5, 7$) was measured.

The chemical composition of the studied glasses was designed as four compositional series: 15Na₂O·10CaO· x ZrO₂·(75- x)SiO₂, $x = 0, 1, 3, 5, 7$ (NCZ); 15K₂O·10CaO· x ZrO₂·(75- x)SiO₂, $x = 0, 1, 3, 5, 7$ (KCZ); 15Na₂O·10ZnO· x ZrO₂·(75- x)SiO₂, $x = 0, 1, 3, 5, 7$ (NzZ); 15K₂O·10ZnO· x ZrO₂·(75- x)SiO₂, $x = 0, 1, 3, 5, 7$ (KzZ).

The glass batches were prepared from analytical grade purity oxides and carbonates. Glasses were melted in Pt-10%Rh crucible in superkanthal furnace at the temperature of 1600°C for two-three hours in ambient atmosphere. The homogeneity was ensured by repeated hand mixing of the melt. The chemical composition of studied glasses was determined after their decomposition by the mixture of HF and HClO₄ by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (VARIAN - Vista MPX / ICP-OES). The content of SiO₂ was not analyzed.

Sessile drops were prepared from the glass cubes of approximate (2×2×2) mm³ dimensions on glassy carbon plate in the atmosphere of pure nitrogen. Pendant drop was obtained by melting of the T-shape glass samples suspended in the platinum wire ring. The drop profile was recorded by the CCD camera and digitized using the Lucia[®] software (LIM, a.s. Prague). The temperature at which the symmetric drop shape was reached during the sample heating with the heating rate of 5°C/min. was chosen as the starting temperature for recording of the drop profile. The values of surface tension were obtained by the least squares method by minimization of the sum of squares of deviations between the experimental and calculated drop profile. The calculated drop profile was obtained by the numerical integration of the Laplace equation using the experimental density values (Table 1). The surface tension was determined over the temperature range (1250-1500)°C using the melt density value obtained by independent experiment.

The composition and temperature dependences of the surface tension were investigated. Linear temperature decrease of measured surface tension was found for all studied glass melts. The effect of isomolar substitutions K₂O/Na₂O, ZnO/CaO and ZrO₂/SiO₂ on surface tension was discussed. On the basis of decreasing surface tension, the components formed in glass from K₂O, CaO and SiO₂ were identified as surface active. The greatest impact on surface tension increasing was observed in the case of ZnO content increasing. The surface tension values obtained by the sessile drop method were in almost all cases little bit lower than those obtained by the pendant drop method. On the other hand the values are identical within the estimated standard deviation.

Table 1: Surface tension values (γ) of studied glassforming melts at 1400°C. Standard deviations of

surface tension $s(\gamma) \leq 2 \text{ mN.m}^{-1}$.

	$\gamma \text{ [mN.m}^{-1}\text{]}$			$\gamma \text{ [mN.m}^{-1}\text{]}$	
	Sessile drop	Pendant drop		Sessile drop	Pendant drop
NCZ0	271	275	NzZ0	286	288
NCZ1	274	279	NzZ1	295	301
NCZ3	280	284	NzZ3	304	307
NCZ5	283	288	NzZ5	311	313
NCZ7	288	292	NzZ7	312	316
KCZ0	190	193	KzZ0	222	219
KCZ1	191	194	KzZ1	233	235
KCZ3	195	196	KzZ3	246	253
KCZ5	205	210	KzZ5	255	258
KCZ7	212	211	KzZ7 ^{*)}	-	-

^{*)}Not measured due to sample crystallization.

Keywords: glass, pendant drop method, sessile drop method, surface tension

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Structure determination of binary phosphate glasses: Combination of Raman spectroscopy and Thermodynamic modeling approach

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ABSTRACT

Since 100 years, different properties of phosphate glasses have been investigated for many different applications including a variety of industrial applications [1], high power laser applications [2, 3], specialty hermetic seals [4], nuclear waste hosts [5] etc. These specific properties are obviously related to the molecular- level glass structures. Therefore, the structural study on various phosphate glasses has significant importance. Usually, solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS), and neutron diffraction analysis provide unprecedented detail of the bonding arrangements in glasses. However, Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva [6] proposed an associated solutions thermodynamic model (extension of Conrad's model) that has been successfully applied to silicate, phosphate and chalcogenide glasses for finding the structure with the help of Raman spectroscopy. This model considers glasses and melts as ideal solutions formed from salt-like products of equilibrium chemical reactions between the simple chemical entities (oxides, chalcogenides, etc.) and from the original (un-reacted) entities. These salt like products have the same stoichiometry as the crystalline compounds, which exist in the equilibrium phase diagram of the considered system. Moreover, in this model molar Gibbs energies of pure crystalline compounds and the analytical composition of the system are used as input parameters.

The aim of the present work is the determination of the structure of glasses of the binary systems P_2O_5 -BaO, P_2O_5 -MgO, P_2O_5 -Na₂O and P_2O_5 -Li₂O by comparison of the results of the thermodynamic model of Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva with the results obtained from the analysis of Raman spectra performed by the Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Multivariate Curve Resolution (MCR) and spectral decomposition by the method of Malfait [7]. PCA method identifies the number of independent components in the studied spectral series. On the other hand, the number of independent components with significant abundance in the studied glasses will be obtained by thermodynamic modeling. Partial Raman spectra of independent components will be calculated by using the method of Malfait. The MCR method has been used for the analysis of the experimental spectra to find the spectra of pure components (so-called weights) and the relative abundances of these components (so-called scores). For investigated glasses, Li₂O, Na₂O, MgO, and BaO dependence of equilibrium molar amounts of the system components at a fixed temperature of 1000 K was calculated by using thermodynamic model (Fig. 1). From Fig. 1, two pseudo-binary regions for Li₂O & Na₂O systems and three pseudo-binary regions for MgO & BaO systems can be found in the glass forming region (content up to 58 mol%).

$0 < x_{\text{glass}}(\text{Li}_2\text{O}) < 0.50 - \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \ \& \ \text{LP}$ $0.50 < x_{\text{glass}}(\text{Li}_2\text{O}) < 0.58 - \text{LP} \ \& \ \text{L2P}$	$0 < x_{\text{glass}}(\text{Na}_2\text{O}) < 0.50 - \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \ \& \ \text{NP}$ $0.50 < x_{\text{glass}}(\text{Na}_2\text{O}) < 0.58 - \text{NP} \ \& \ \text{N5P3} \ \& \ \text{N2P}$
$0 < x_{\text{glass}}(\text{MgO}) < 0.33 - \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \ \& \ \text{MP2}$ $0.33 < x_{\text{glass}}(\text{MgO}) < 0.50 - \text{MP2} \ \& \ \text{MP}$ $0.50 < x_{\text{glass}}(\text{MgO}) < 0.58 - \text{MP} \ \& \ \text{M2P}$	$0 < x_{\text{glass}}(\text{BaO}) < 0.33 - \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \ \& \ \text{BP2}$ $0.33 < x_{\text{glass}}(\text{BaO}) < 0.50 - \text{BP2} \ \& \ \text{BP}$ $0.50 < x_{\text{glass}}(\text{BaO}) < 0.58 - \text{BP} \ \& \ \text{B2P}$

Fig. 1: X_{glass} a) Li₂O, b) Na₂O, c) MgO, and d) BaO dependence of equilibrium molar amounts of the system components in investigated glasses at fixed temperature of T= 1000 K.

Keywords: Phosphate glasses, Structure, Thermodynamic model.

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OPTICAL MATERIALS

Y2O3- the way to transparent ceramics

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ABSTRACT

Y2O3 ceramics have been studied for many years because of their promising properties like high corrosion resistance, high melting point (2425°C) low thermal expansion coefficient and relatively high heat conductivity which can be critical for temperature management. Having cubic crystallographic unit, it is easier to create transparent ceramics since it is isotropic environment for electromagnetic radiation. Applications ranges from transparent windows to missile domes, bulb envelopes, and laser hosts ^{1,2} When compared to other transparent materials such as Al₂O₃, AlON and MgAl₂O₄ (spinel), the Y2O3 has a far lower emissivity and a smaller absorption coefficient in the IR part of spectra at elevated temperatures³. These characteristics make it an excellent IR window material for high-temperature applications.

Experimental procedure. The starting fine grained Y2O3 powder was produced by PENGDA with reported particle size of 150nm. We prepared three suspensions:

PEN9: Water based suspension with 5 Vol% of yttria, stabilized by DarvanCN (1.5wt%). Suspension was dispersed by 8 minutes of ultrasonication.

PEN10: Isopropanol based suspension with 10 vol% of yttria, stabilized by PEG (1wt%). Suspension was dispersed by ball milling for 4 days. Part of suspension was dispersed for 2 minutes by ultrasonication and designed as **PEN10UZ**.

PEN11UZ: Isopropanol based suspension with 3 vol% of yttria, stabilized by PEG (1wt%) Suspension was dispersed for 2 minutes by ultrasonication.

All suspensions were analyzed by Particle Size Analyzer (90Plus, f. Brookhaven) (Fig. 1). Analysis shows that water based suspension is dispersed to highest degree but it is far from mean grain size of 150nm declared by Pengda manufacturer and even further from grain size of about 80nm obtained with help of SEM. Isopropanol based suspension shows low effectivity of ball milling (Pen 10) and somewhat better effectivity of ultrasonic disperzation (PEN10UZ). Lowering the solid load of yttria down to 3 vol.% resulted to profoundly better disperzation. Yet the solid load of 3vol.% proves to be too low because it allows to create only thin green bodies which leads to impossibility to polish away structural defects on surface after sintering. All suspensions were pressure filtrated at 50 MPa pressure to obtain green body pellets. Pellets were then dried in oven at 40°C for 12 hours. For comparison reasons, we prepared specimens designed as **I** and **IA** which were made by dry pressing of Y₂O₃ powder and specimens designed as **II** and **IIA** which were made by dry pressing of annealed yttria powder (700°C for 5 hours).

All green body pellets were sintered with the temperature regime: 5°C/min to 80°C and 2 hours of dwell time; followed by 5°C/min to 120°C and 2hours of dwell time and finally 10°C/min to 1600°C and 1hour of dwell time followed by free cooling.

After sintering, the homogeneity of specimens was evaluated visually with help of crossing light. The worst quality we observed by dry pressed specimens where darker spots were present (the light was locally more dispersed on inhomogeneity's). Better internal quality was observed on water

suspension based specimens. Best quality of translucence was observed by specimens prepared from isopropanol based suspensions.

PEN 9	PEN 9A	PEN 10	PEN 10UZ	PEN 11	I	IA	II	IIA
98.80%	98.20%	99.00%	99.00%	98.60%	97.41%	96.41%	97.21%	96.81%

Table 1. Relative density of sintered specimens

All the specimens were measured for density by Archimedes method in water (Table 1). Pressure filtered samples showed superior density compared to dry pressed specimens.

Measurements of Vickers hardness at 1kg load/10s (Fig. 2.) showed average hardness of about 7- 8 GPa which is similar to results found in literature⁴.

Future work plans will involve further optimization of water and isopropanol based suspensions preparation for pressure filtration, optimization of sintering process and application of HIP to reach fully transparent specimens. Additions of optically active elements will be included to obtain transparent luminescent materials.

Keywords: Dry pressing, Pressure filtration, Y2O3 ceramics

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Eu²⁺-doped Y₂O₃-Al₂O₃ system with and without charge compensation

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ABSTRACT

The spectroscopic properties of phosphors result from the energy levels of the doping ion (rare earth – RE, transition metal – TM, or others), which are affected by crystal field [1]. Indeed, in certain cases (e.g. Ce³⁺, Eu²⁺ etc.), the energy levels of particular photoluminescence centre can be effectively tuned by the crystal field strength of a host matrix thus producing the emissions from blue to red spectral range. Luminescent materials are widely applied today and the major applications are solid-state lighting (SSL) systems [1-3].

The yttrium aluminium garnet Y₃Al₅O₁₂ (YAG) have been used as a host material for lasers and phosphors for their excellent luminescent properties, remarkable chemical stability at high temperatures, pronounced corrosion resistance, good mechanical properties, and excellent structural compatibility [4, 5].

Various methods have been utilized to synthesize YAG-based phosphors. Nevertheless, it is difficult to obtain Eu²⁺-doped YAG phosphor through conventional methods, such as synthesis under reduction atmosphere, because Eu³⁺ is very difficult to reduce to Eu²⁺ ion in the YAG crystal lattice. On the other hand, the frequently used Eu₂O₃ is very stable and cannot be reduced to Eu²⁺ at low temperatures [6, 7].

In this work, we report the preparation of Eu³⁺/Eu²⁺-doped Y₂O₃-Al₂O₃ glass by combination of the sol-gel method based precursor synthesis and flame spraying technique. The glass and corresponding polycrystalline glass-ceramics were characterized and their thermal, structural, and photoluminescence properties were studied in detail.

The Eu³⁺ doped glass in the Y₂O₃-Al₂O₃ system with eutectic composition (76.86 mol. % (60 wt. %) Al₂O₃ and 23.13 mol. % (40 wt. %) Y₂O₃, corresponding to ~50 mol. % of YAG and ~50 mol. % of Al₂O₃) were prepared by flame-spraying synthesis in the form of glass microspheres from precursor powder synthesized by Pechini sol-gel method. The doping level ranges from 0.5 to 2.0 at. % of Eu³⁺. The prepared glass microspheres were found to be almost XRD amorphous. The DSC analysis revealed the two exothermic effects corresponding to crystallization of glass at characteristic temperatures. The origin of the two crystallization peaks examined by high temperature XRD (HT XRD) revealed the crystallization of YAG phase (Y₃Al₅O₁₂) up to 1200 °C. The both exothermic effects thus unusually correspond to YAG phase crystallization; the first peak mainly to nucleation and partial crystallization of YAG phase, the second peak to crystal growth of YAG phase. The polycrystalline phosphors were prepared from glass by controlled crystallization at selected time-temperature regime. The photoluminescence (PL) properties of glass and polycrystalline phosphors were studied in detail. In as prepared glass, the both oxidation states of europium, Eu³⁺ and Eu²⁺, were found to coexist in glass matrix. The emission spectra of Eu³⁺ glasses under UV excitation at 393 nm exhibit intensive red emission in the spectral range of 570-720 nm, while Eu²⁺ containing glass (excited at 345 nm) emit the light in broad spectral range from 400-700 nm with the emission maximum at ~520 nm. The PL properties of Eu³⁺/Eu²⁺-doped glass and corresponding

polycrystalline phosphors were compared. The charge compensation effect on PL properties and $\text{Eu}^{3+}/\text{Eu}^{2+}$ equilibria was also examined. The prepared phosphors belongs to the family of good candidates for pc-WLED under UV light excitation.

Keywords: aluminate glass, $\text{Eu}^{3+}/\text{Eu}^{2+}$, glass, phosphor, photoluminescence, YAG

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Solid-state fabrication of transparent YAG ceramics with submicron microstructure for optical applications

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Transparent ceramic materials are commonly realized as the next generation of solid-state lasers due to their unique features such as high thermal and chemical stability, better uniformity, high optical quality, and flexibility in large sized production, compared with its single crystal counterparts. Polycrystalline yttrium aluminum garnet ceramic laser material ($\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$) or YAG is one of the most common candidates that received much attention since 1995 due to its optical characteristics that has been improved greatly and its highly efficient laser oscillation that could be obtained [1]. Moreover, in the case of laser applications, some recent works demonstrated the rare-earth-doped YAG ceramics to be even better than the single crystals [2,3].

For the last thirty years, massive attention has been focused on the performance of YAG ceramics fabrication methods [4-7]. Compared with the complicated wet-chemical techniques of YAG nanopowders synthesis [8,9] the solid-state reactive sintering is considered as the easiest and cost efficient way for achieving of YAG desired properties. In this way, commercial high purity $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and Y_2O_3 powders are mixed in precise stoichiometric quantities where the required YAG phase transformation occurs during the sintering step.

It is well known that the microstructure and optical properties of YAG ceramics are completely related to the purity, morphology, particle size, and particle size distribution of the starting powders. Accordingly, pretreatment of the commercially used powders represents a remarkable importance where it will be observably reflected on the produced microstructure. On the other hand, it has been proved that the Al_2O_3 - Y_2O_3 system experienced three different crystallographic phases during the reaction or sintering: monoclinic phase (YAM, $\text{Y}_4\text{Al}_2\text{O}_9$), perovskite phase (YAP, YAlO_3), and cubic phase (YAG, $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$). The phase composition and formation temperature ranges for each phase are described as follows [10]:

So, great attention has to be paid during the sintering reaction to avoid the presence of any secondary YAP or YAM phases which interfere with the YAG cubic structure and inhibit the propagation of light through the material thus strongly deteriorating the optical properties. Moreover, the most important issue in the transparent YAG ceramics is the removal of pores, which is achieved through the use of sintering additive and application of vacuum or pressure during sintering. Although tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) and MgO served as a common sintering additive for the densification promotion [11-13], the priority was given to the use of MgO where a successful fabrication of YAG transparent ceramic with excellent optical properties was achieved by employing a simple solid state reaction vacuum sintering using MgO single dopant as sintering aid. The transmittance was 84.5% at 1064 nm, after sintering the sample at 1820°C for 8 h, when the concentration of MgO was only 0.03 wt. % [13].

It is proposed to use the solid-state reaction for the fabrication of transparent YAG and Nd:YAG ceramics with submicron microstructure. High purity commercial α -Al₂O₃, pre-treated Y₂O₃, Nd₂O₃ powders will be mixed using planetary mill. MgO will be used as a sintering aid. The powders will be uniaxially pressed prior to cold isostatic pressing and after vacuum sintering at different temperature (1760–1820°C) the samples will go for annealing in air at different temperatures to eliminate the oxygen vacancies. After mirror polishing on both sides the samples will be studied for the optical properties, then etched to expose the grain boundaries for the microstructural study. The optimized conditions will be adjusted for further study using transition elements as dopants.

Keywords: Solid-state reaction, YAG transparent ceramics, Vacuum sintering.

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Transparent YAG Ceramic / Partial Results

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ABSTRACT

Yttrium aluminium garnet ($Y_3Al_5O_{12}$, YAG) ceramic is a candidate for applications of high-temperature structural materials and refractory coatings for electronic devices due to its low creep rate, high thermal stability and good chemical resistance, and it is widely used in lasers as a host for rare-earth-based phosphors [1, 2].

Most transparent YAG ceramics are fabricated by calcining starting materials into pure YAG phase and then sintering into YAG ceramics or via solid state reaction of alumina and yttria powders [3]. Because sol-gel method has the apparent advantages of fine homogeneity, high reactivity of starting materials and lower heat-treated temperature, it has attracted more and more attention [4]. In this process, gelation is obtained from a solution of inorganic metal salts and a complexing agent.

In this method, a citrate solution containing the metal ions is converted into a gel, which is dried and subsequently calcined to form the oxide powder (YAG). A uniform distribution of metal ions in the precursor can be maintained throughout the process. In the present study, synthesis of YAG by citrate-gel method using nitrates of the metals and citric acid has been carried out.

The presented work describes the first step in a project focused on the preparation of transparent YAG ceramic. In order to achieve transparency of YAG ceramic the stoichiometric composition between alumina and yttria has to be precise; however, in some of prepared YAG precursors Y_2O_3 was detected by XRD analysis (blue arrows in **Fig. 1**).

Fig. 1: XRD pattern of prepared YAG precursors

Nevertheless, alumina was not identified by the XRD analysis. This implies that there was not sufficient amount of Al^{3+} in the system, or alumina has an amorphous structure. Annealing of aluminium nitrate nonahydrate revealed that beside the purity of used chemical (98 %), important role plays hygroscopic character of this powder. Therefore, prior to each sol-gel process, annealing of aluminium nitrate nonahydrate has to be performed in order to find out the actual amount of water bonded to aluminium nitrate.

Sinterability of prepared pure YAG powders was detected by the TMA (thermomechanical analysis) with and without using the sintering aid (1 wt. % LiF).

The results will be discussed at the FunGlass Seminar on Functional Materials.

Keywords: sol-gel process, TMA, XRD, YAG

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Transparent YAG Glass / Partial Results

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ABSTRACT

Transparent ceramics become more and more important for applications, in which materials are subject to extremely high mechanical and thermal stress in combination with optical properties. More recently, interest has focused on the development of transparent armor materials (ceramic) for both military and civil applications. Also, the development of new optoelectronic devices has extended the use of ordinary optical materials to new applications and environments such as temperature (IR) sensor, optical fiber communications, laser interferometers, etc. A considerable fraction of these new devices operates in aggressive environments, such as ovens, radiation chambers and aerospace sensors. In such cases, the sensitive electronic component must be preserved from the extreme external condition by a transparent window [1].

In science and technology the word transparent is used for those components that show clear images regardless of the distance between the object and the transparent window. Clear transparency is achieved when after transmission through the window the light does not undergo noticeable absorption or scattering. This applies, for example, to some glasses, single-crystalline and polycrystalline transparent ceramics.

Yttrium aluminium garnet ($\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$, YAG) is a polycrystalline material, which has a cubic structure that can be used in structural and functional applications. YAG has been considered a prime candidate for its use as a matrix in oxide-oxide composites in gas turbine engines [2]. Also, it can be used as substrate for dielectric components, prisms and mirrors, as a part of discharge lamps, high intensity lamps as well as an active medium for the production of lasers [3], since it is able to accept trivalent cations in its structure, especially rare earths and transition metals. Three stable phases exist in the Y_2O_3 - Al_2O_3 system: an orthorhombic perovskite YAlO_3 (“YAP”) with an Y/Al ratio 1:1, an alumina-rich cubic garnet $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (“YAG”), and an yttria rich monoclinic phase with composition $\text{Y}_4\text{Al}_2\text{O}_9$ (“YAM”).

Although many transparent ceramics are single crystal materials, transparent polycrystalline ceramics have different advantages such as low price, ease of manufacture, mass-production and more versatility in properties. Polycrystalline ceramics are usually manufactured by compacting powder to a body, which is then sintered at high temperatures. Fully dense bulk articles in net shape are obtained through viscous sintering of glass microbeads [4, 5].

We want to prepare by hot press technique transparent bulk glass material from YAG glass microspheres by flame spheroidization process in oxygen-methane (O_2/CH_4) flame in sintering window $\Delta T = T_x - T_g$. The precursor powders for flame synthesis were prepared by mixing $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (p.a., Centralchem, Bratislava), dissolved in deionized water with yttrium nitrate prepared by dissolution of Y_2O_3 powder (Treibacher Industrie AG, Austria) in 65% HNO_3 in the Al/Y molar ratio identical to that in the yttrium-aluminium garnet $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$. Citric acid dissolved in deionized water and ethyleneglycol were added to the solution and the mixture was heated in oil bath for 2 hours at 85-90°C. The dried product was calcined at 1000°C for 4 hours in air and sieved through a 25-40 μm analytical sieve.

The calcined powder (25-40 μm) was fed into an oxygen-methane (O_2/CH_4) torch with a vacuum

powder feeder at a rate of 2 g/min using oxygen carrier gas. The spherical melt particles were formed in high temperature oxy-methane flame (estimated temperature 2800°C) and then quenched by spraying by distilled water to form solid glass microspheres (SGMs). The SGMs were separated from distilled water by microfiltration through a ceramic filter with pore size < 0.3 µm.

The glass transition temperatures (T_g) and onset crystallization temperatures (T_x) of glass microspheres were evaluated from room temperature to 1100°C by DSC method at three different heating rates (5, 10 and 20°C/min). The amorphous nature of SGMs was confirmed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and the morphology of the solid glass microspheres was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The next step will be preparation of bulk glass (ϕ 10 mm) out of SGMs by vacuum hot press sintering at corresponding sintering window temperatures. Subsequently, the YAG glass or glass-ceramic pellets will be investigated by SEM and XRD analysis.

Keywords: flame synthesis, hot pressing, YAG glass.

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Spark Plasma Sintering and Sol-Gel: Alternative methods to obtain oxyfluoride glass-ceramics for optical applications

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ABSTRACT

RE-doped oxyfluoride glass-ceramics (GCs) are currently being widely investigated for its use as white light emitting diodes (wLEDs,) solar cells and catalysis and other photonics applications. This type of materials has unique properties combining the good mechanical, thermal and chemical properties of an oxide glass matrix with the low phonon energy of crystalline fluoride environments ($250\text{-}450\text{ cm}^{-1}$) that reduces non-radiative multiphonon relaxations. Moreover, GCs present a high degree of transparency due to the much smaller size of dispersed nanocrystals (NCs) in the amorphous matrix, less than 50 nm avoiding the Rayleigh scattering, which is very important for their practical applications. In this sense, oxyfluoride glass-ceramics doped with trivalent lanthanide ions (Ln^{3+}) acquired a great interest owing to their attractive optical properties and potential applications as luminescent materials [1,2].

The use of luminescent GCs in photonic applications requires the development of the following properties:

- (i) Strong absorption bands ranging from visible to infrared light for efficient pumping.
- (ii) Good luminescence efficiency. Incident rays must be effectively transformed into longer-wave luminescence.
- (iii) A high-quality optical medium is necessary to avoid energy losses due to scattering, absorption by the impurities should be low during absorption and the transformation of the energy.
- (iv) To use the glass-ceramics in technological processes, it is necessary to produce large sizes of the materials. Therefore, the manufacturing procedures involving melting and processing of the glasses to form glass-ceramics must be economically feasible.

Among the different methods from which GCs can be obtained, Melting-quenching (MQ) method is the most use. Due to high melting temperature and high heat treatments for obtaining crystallization in precursor glass matrix through melt quenching technique, fluorine loss is high. This is one of the main limiting factors for fluorine-based compositions. In order to avoid this fluorine loss, alternative methods have been proposed such as Spark plasma sintering (SPS) and sol-gel methods.

From those of them, SPS method is a rapid sintering technique that combines uniaxial pressure with elevated temperature generated by current flow, thus it enables fast densification at low sintering temperatures and with very small grain size. Specific advantages of SPS over conventional sintering techniques are; faster heating rate and low sintering temperature (shorter dwell time) [3], quick powder consolidation. The materials produced have been reported to have improved properties relative to those obtained by other consolidation methods, e.g., hot-pressing. In this method, selected glass compositions have been melted in a platinum crucible in the temperature range $1200\text{-}1650^\circ\text{C}$ depending on the glass composition for 2-4 hours with intermittent stirring. Further homogenization could be achieved by crushing and re-melting. Monolithic glass precursor is obtained by casting followed by annealing. Prepared glasses can be followed again two ways to obtain GCs via ceramization of precursor glass sample with controlled heat treatment and another one through powder sintering directly. The major activity in this optimization of technological parameters such as temperature and time of precursor glass melting, refining and annealing, and nucleation and nanostructuring of glass-ceramics because all these parameters vary with glass composition. Using SPS method (powder sintering), the following stages

will be adopted:

- Preparation of glasses in the system $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Na}_2\text{O-K}_2\text{O-La/Y/Gd/LuF}_3$ in which different fluoride phases can precipitate (KLaF_4 , NaLaF_4 , NaLuF_4 ...) under the suitable thermal treatment and doped with Nd/Tm.
- Optimization of the sintering-crystallization conditions by SPS: particle size of the glass powder, power, heating rate, applied pressure, dwell temperature and time.
- Characterization of glasses and glass-ceramics by (HR-TEM and STEM). Study of the phase separation and Crystallization processes. Size distribution and elemental analysis of crystals, matrix and interphases. Location and concentration of dopants in the crystals and glass matrix.
- Study of the optical properties.

On the other hand, materials prepared via sol-gel processing involve the generation of colloidal suspensions (sols) which are subsequently converted to viscous gels and then to solid materials called xerogels/aerogels (depending of drying conditions). Through this method, it is possible to increase the amount of fluoride in the composition using low temperature processing and with high homogeneity [4,5].

In each case temperature of sol-gel-xerogel procedures is in general definitely below the crystallization temperature for oxide materials and it allows to produce unusual amorphous materials and composites like GCs after adequate heat treatments. Using sol-gel method, the following stages have to be adopted:

- Optimization of the sol-gel synthesis: molar ratio of precursors, solvents and dopants, control of pH, temperature and room conditions to obtain stable sols.
- Preparation of crack-free and homogeneous GCs coatings studying the heat treatment process.
- Study of structure and crystallization processes of GCs coatings to obtain good crystallization and crystal size. Preparation of novel rare-earth doped nanostructured glass-ceramics films. Characterization of the materials using: DTA/DSC, XRD, HRTEM, SEM, NMR and UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer etc.

Finally, the main aim of the study is to determine chemical and physical conditions more adequate to prepare oxyfluoride glass-ceramic materials with good optical properties by spark plasma sintering and sol-gel procedures. The second aim is to provide more information about the crystallization process (relation between microstructure, processing and properties) and the effect of the incorporation of different rare earth (example: Tm^{3+} and Nd^{3+}) ion doping on excitation, emission, lifetimes and cross-relaxation studies.

Keywords: Oxyfluoride glass ceramics; spark plasma sintering (SPS); sol-gel; nanocrystal; optical properties.

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Synthesis of Ce³⁺ doped Yttria nanopowders by precipitation method for transparent yttria ceramics

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Transparent ceramics are attractive optical materials that offer many advantages over single crystals, including better shape control, higher homogeneity of dopant distribution, and faster and lower cost fabrication methods [1]. Transparent polycrystalline ceramic can be used as replacement of glass and single crystals in production of solid state lasers. The main strategies to ensure high optical quality of transparent ceramics include controlling the purity, particle size, and homogeneity of the precursor materials, exploring and understanding the sintering mechanisms of different materials, and the use of advanced sintering techniques [2]. Ceramic processing typically consists of three main steps: (i) synthesis or preparation of precursor powders, (ii) consolidation or packing of the powders into green bodies, and (iii) sintering [3]. Yttria (Y₂O₃) is widely known as a promising optical material owing to its broad range transparency, high melting temperature (2430°C), outstanding refractoriness and excellent chemical stability. Therefore, polycrystalline transparent yttria ceramics have been exploited as perfect candidate to replace single crystals. Over past few decades, transparent yttria ceramics have been shown to possess great potential in various applications, including transparent windows, missile domes, solid state lasers. Y₂O₃ transparent ceramics are also very efficient NIR-visible up-converters, and can be used as materials for X-ray scintillator applications bulb envelopes and laser hosts [4]. However, the fabrication of high performance transparent yttria ceramics is not an easy task, as the complete elimination of residual pores is essential in spite of high melting point of yttria. Therefore, high sintering temperatures, suitable additives and specific sintering techniques must be applied in order to accelerate the densification of yttria. Successful preparation of transparent polycrystalline ceramics also requires high purity nanopowders with good sinterability and deagglomerated particles. In this work preparation of Ce-doped Y₂O₃ nanopowders by precipitation method using ammonium hydroxide as precipitation agent is reported and discussed.

Figure 1 SEM micrograph of the prepared Y₂O₃ powder

Y_2O_3 nanopowders prepared by precipitation method, using yttrium nitrate and cerium nitrate solution, 0.5N ammonium hydroxide as precipitation agent. The washed precipitate was dried overnight in air at 100°C. The dried precipitate was crushed and ground in an agate mortar and pestle, and calcined in air for 3 h at 700°C. Ultrasonication was then used to de-agglomerate the nanopowder, using calculated amounts of Y_2O_3 powder and ammonium solution to adjust the pH value of the suspension. After sonication particle size and particle size distribution were determined as a function of pH and sonication time using particle size analyser. The influence of different dispersant addition on suspension behaviour of Ce doped yttria powder was studied. Green compact prepared by pressure filtration method.

Figure 2 The change of particle size distributions of the Y_2O_3 powder with the sonication time.

The influence of precipitation agent and concentration of reactants, morphology, particle size and degree of agglomeration was evaluated. Partly agglomerated powders with the primary size of Y_2O_3 nanoparticles ~200 nm with cubic crystal structure were prepared. The optimum concentration of ammonia precipitation agent was found to be 0.5N. Ultrasonic deagglomeration of the powder was most efficient if the pH value was adjusted to 11 through addition of NH_4OH solution. Dolapix CE64 is more effective dispersant compare with Darvan CN. The green compact has about 40% of density prepared by pressure filtration method.

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Preparation / Characterisation

Preparation of Precursor Materials in the Al₂O₃-Y₂O₃ System by Modified Sol-Gel Pechini Method

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ABSTRACT

The large amount (400g) of AYE precursor powder with eutectic composition (76.8 mol.% Al₂O₃, 23.2 mol.% Y₂O₃) was prepared by modified sol-gel Pechini method. In order to prepare starting powder with high level of homogeneity and very fine particle size distribution, the new apparatus was built and conditions of sol-gel Pechini method were modified. The prepared precursor powder was used as starting materials for flame synthesis of glass microspheres. The both materials (prepared starting powders and glass microspheres) were examined by XRD for study of phase composition of precursor powders, and to confirm amorphous nature of prepared glass bodies. The prepared precursor powders were polycrystalline with presence only pure YAG (yttrium- aluminium garnet) phase. The X-ray diffraction patterns of prepared glass microspheres showed fully amorphous nature, without presence of YAG crystalline phase.

KEYWORDS: sol-gel method, YAG, eutectic microstructure, flame synthesis

INTRODUCTION

Rare earth aluminate-based materials with eutectic microstructures represent an interesting approach to ceramics with important mechanical properties (hardness, fracture strength /toughness), thermal stability and creep resistance at elevated temperatures. These properties are attributed to strong eutectic interfaces between present phases and designate these materials for various aerospace (jet aircraft engines) and industrial (high efficiency power generation gas turbines components) applications. The combination of precipitation method and flame synthesis was used for preparation of glass microspheres with eutectic composition in system Al₂O₃-Y₂O₃ in our previous work [1]. The prepared microspheres were HP (hot press) sintered at different temperatures and different holding times. IR transparent ceramics and glass ceramics with fine two phase microstructure with Al₂O₃ and YAG phases percolating at submicrometre level and with hardness exceeding 15 GPa resulted from the experiments. In this work, the yttrium-aluminate glass microspheres with eutectic compositions were prepared by combination of sol-gel Pechini [2] method and flame synthesis to achieve a better compositional homogeneity of glass microspheres and improved mechanical properties of final bulk ceramic materials. The prepared precursor powders and glass microspheres were examined by XRD and results are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

The precursor powders containing 76.8 mol.% Al₂O₃ and 23.2 mol.% Y₂O₃ were prepared by modified Pechini sol-gel method. On the first step solutions of aluminium nitrate (Al(NO₃)₃.9H₂O; 99.9%;Sigma Aldrich, Germany dissolved in deionized water) and yttrium nitrate (Y₂O₃; 99.9%, Treibacher Industry, Austria dissolved in diluted nitric acid) were prepared. These solutions were mixed and homogenized at temperature 60°C for 1 hour. An aqueous solution of citric acid and ethylene glycol in the molar ratio 1:1 was then prepared and added to mixture of nitrates. The results solution was homogenized under reflux at temperature 75°C for 3 hours. After then the mixture was heated in the heating nest at

temperature 150°C under Liebig cooler to promote polymerization, and to efficiently evaporate the water (at ~ 120°C) and nitride oxides (at ~ 145°C). This way prepared resulting product was put into oven and was calcined in two steps (650°C for 6 hours and 1000°C for 6 hours) in the ambient atmosphere. Finally, the prepared powders were sieved through 40 µm sieves to obtain narrow fraction for flame synthesis, and the phase composition of precursor powder was examined by X-ray powder diffraction analysis. Then the precursor powders were fed into methane-oxygen flame where the powder particles were remelted and subsequently were cooled with distilled water. On the last step, the prepared glass bodies were collected and separated. The prepared glass microspheres were examined by XRD analysis to confirm their amorphous nature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of XRD examination of prepared powders and glass microspheres are shown in Fig.1. The prepared powder was polycrystalline with content of only pure YAG (JCPDS 88-2048) phase. The samples of prepared glass microspheres were XRD amorphous. On the next time, the crystallisation experiments will be performed for more detailed study of crystallisation behaviour of prepared glass system.

Fig.1 The X-ray diffraction patterns of precursor powder (after calcination at 1000°C) (a) and prepared glass microspheres (b)

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Investigation of layered coloured glass using laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry

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Nowadays laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) tends to be one of the standard analytical methods for archaeological glass characterization together with Scanning Electron Microscopy with Energy or Wavelength Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS or WDS). One of the main interest of this paper is to optimize method for depth and surface profile analysis using the time-resolution analytical mode. The glass artefacts are very often partially or fully corroded. These layers overlay the original glass bulk which results in misleading information about chemical composition. In addition, the bulk-compositional data can be retrieved to provide information about fabrication technique and provenance of the raw materials (sands, fluxes, chromophores, opacifiers etc.) in order to address specific questions, particularly in disciplines such as conservation-restoration. In this paper compositional characterization of a multi-layered glass object was elaborated. Optimization of spot size and scan speed were discussed in order to improve ablation efficiency in other words the crater properties and transport efficiency. SEM-EDS/WDS was used as a comparative technique for cross-section evaluation of a multi-layered glass fragment.

EXPERIMENTAL

Glass fragment was found in the central part of the Czech Republic near Havlíčkov Brod, at a site of abandoned workshop producing glass between 18th and 19th Century. The glass fragment of blurry pink colour observed with naked eye shows signs of corrosion (Fig. 1). Despite the small dimension of fragment, part of it was cut and embedded in epoxy resin to prepare sample for cross-section observation. Prior to analysis the sample embedded in epoxy was polished and coated with thin layer of carbon ~10 nm. Bulk composition was determined with INCA energy

Fig. 1: Finding of glass fragment from central part of the Czech Republic.

and wave dispersive X-ray spectrometer. For quantitative elemental analysis, the point analysis was carried out at a magnification of 250 \times for 100s at 15 kV accelerating potential and working distance 15 mm.

LA-ICP-MS measurements were performed with Nd:YAG laser ablation system with wavelength 213 nm and laser pulse width < 5ns. The spot size <50 μm , energy in a range from 10 to 90%, frequency 15 Hz and rates from 1 to 50 $\mu\text{m/s}$ were considered to tune conditions for depth ablation analysis (LA). The applied energy (E) of laser 45%, corresponding value of fluence ~ 6.7 J/cm², was selected as optimal value with sufficient sensitivity and the lowest RSD %, i.e. the lowest probability to fractionation. The energy optimization was performed with NIST

612 standard. The same standard was included in quantification analysis. Tuning plasma parameters to the following values: the carrier gas (0.55 ml/min), sampling depth (8 mm) and the flow of helium as a collision gas setting up to the value of 1ml/min was carried out in order to minimize the oxide polyatomic interferences. Resulted oxide ratio of ²⁴⁸ThO/²³²Th was below 1%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cross-section examination with the scanning electron microscopy (Fig. 2) revealed three layers: outer and inner opacified layer and in between compositionally different intermediate layer of thickness $\sim 170 \mu\text{m}$. Prior to detailed LA-ICP-MS analysis, the chemical composition of all layers was examined with SEM EDS. The outer and inner layer compositionally belong to the group of potash-lime-silica-glasses ($9 \text{ K}_2\text{O}$; 2 CaO ; 78.5 SiO_2 in wt%), while the intermediate

Fig. 2: SEM image from cross-section examination of glass fragment.

Fig. 3: Time resolved line profile through the outer and intermediate chromatic layer.

layer with PbO content close to 7 wt% more to the lead-silica glass. Detailed WDS examination of the intermediate chromatic layer enriched with Pb, did not confirmed presence of other elements. The usual metals present and responsible for pink or ruby colour are Cu, Mn accompanied with electron donors as Sn, Fe. Expected detection limit for mentioned elements is probably above 100 ppm. In the colourless opacified outer and inner layer, inhomogeneities like partially melted stones of various shapes and dimension were randomly scattered in bulk.

The qualitative and quantitative LA-ICP-MS was performed to confirm or evaluate presence of another metals in chromatic layer. For line-scan analysis the laser was operated at a frequency of 15 Hz, using a 30 and 10 μm spot size that delivered $\sim 6.3\text{-}6.8 \text{ J/cm}^2$ of energy along a line pattern with the sample moving at 5.22 microns per second. Scans using LA-ICP-MS (Fig. 3) confirm and expand the findings from EDS/WDS. In the chromatic layer along Pb (6.7 wt%) following metals were identified As (0.35 wt%), Sn (0.15 wt%), Fe, Cu (~ 200 ppm) and Mn (86 ppm). Copper and manganese might be responsible for pink colour generation in the intermediate chromatic layer. Copper may exist in glasses as cuprous ions (Cu^+), which are virtually colourless, however when reducing conditions are sufficient, copper metal may precipitate from the glass. Sufficiently small particles of metallic copper are responsible for translucent ruby red colour in glass. In order for the copper to reduce to metal (Cu^0), there is a need for the Cu^+ ions in the glass to gain an electron. The electron donor can be a polyvalent cation such as Sn^{2+} or another the most likely candidate can be ferrous iron (Fe^{2+}).

CONCLUSION: Mass spectrometry performed in time-resolved analysis mode was selected for compositional characterization of a multi-layered glass object to detect the colour generated metals with the content $< 0.02\text{wt}\%$. Unlike for SEM-EDS/WDS traces of isotopes ^{55}Mn and ^{63}Cu (< 200 ppm) were detected with laser ablation sampling evaluating the intermediate coloured layer.

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Impedance spectroscopy of barium crystal glass

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ABSTRACT

Measurement and Analysis of electromagnetic response – conductive and dielectric properties as a function of frequency, is generally called electrical impedance spectroscopy, admittance spectroscopy, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, dielectric relaxation spectroscopy, or sometimes ac spectroscopy [1]. The technique involves the measurement of the sinusoidal component of the current flowing through the sample, resulting from the sinusoidal voltage, applied across two terminals of a sample. The ratio of measured current to applied voltage and the phase between the two sinus signals, is the complex impedance [2].

The technique can be also used to study the collective response of microscopic polarization processes under external electric field. It is useful and important general electrical characterization tool in materials research and development when studying defects, microstructure, surface chemistry and electrical conductivity for a wide range materials, including dielectrics and ionic conductors.

At our workplace FunGlass we have a general purpose Electrical Impedance Analyzer to perform various electrical measurements [3]. The flexible available software ModuLab MTS allows the semiconductor research scientist to build measurement capability depending upon a chosen experiment and AC/DC levels applicable for each measurement. The system can be configured to measure also time domain signals. AC Impedance or combination of AC and DC measurements, inclusive high resolution, high accuracy femto-ammeter option for leakage current tests in high impedance samples makes the whole system very useful. In order to increase accuracy of the measurements, Sample/Reference Module is available for the investigation of dielectric materials, such as glass.

Impedance spectroscopy experimental method is at FunGlass practically new. This paper deals with results and problems encountered, when calibrating the system and its performance. The issues that will be discussed include the connections within measuring equipment, methodology of measurement, preparation of the samples and the first results. Barium Crystal Glass has been chosen as first “test case” material for these investigations.

Keywords: impedance spectroscopy, dielectric properties, barium glass

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The coatings preparation by sol-gel method

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ABSTRACT

The sol – gel methods can be defined as processes of preparation of inorganic, especially oxidic, materials by the procedures during which the sol is formed at first and then, subsequently, is formed the gel. Sol is a stable dispersion of firm colloid particles in a liquid. Gel is a continuous firm frame created from colloid particles that is closed by a liquid phase. The first step in sol-gel procedures is the creation of sol, that changes itself spontaneously into gel – slowly or quickly, according to the preparation conditions. Sols are often prepared by hydrolysis of metal alkoxides. Silicate sols are most often synthesized by hydrolysing monomeric, tetrafunctional alkoxide precursors employing a mineral acid (e.g., HNO₃) or base (e.g., NH₃) as a catalyst. At the functional group level, three reactions are generally used to describe the sol-gel process:

Where R is an alkyl group, C_xH_{2x+1}. The hydrolysis reaction replaces alkoxide groups (OR) with hydroxyl groups (OH). Subsequent condensation reactions involving the silanol groups produce siloxane bonds (Si-O-Si) plus the by-products alcohol (ROH) or water. Under most conditions, condensation commences before hydrolysis is complete.

The hydrolysis of silicon alkoxides can be described by following summative equation:

However, even in excess water, the reaction does not to completion. Instead, a spectrum of intermediate species ([SiO_x(OH)_y(OR)_z]_n where 2x+y+z=4) are generated.

Typical sol-gel procedures used to produce bulk gels, films, fibers, and powders are listed in Fig.1.

Fig.1 Typical sol-gel procedures.

The coatings, which we prepared by sol-gel method.

Oxidic coatings:

- SiO_2 Anti – reflection layers, materials protection, dielectric layers
- TiO_2 Reflection layers, environmental applications, sensors, photovoltaic applications
- ZrO_2 Materials protection, optic applications
- $\text{SiO}_2 - \text{TiO}_2$ Index of refraction can be fluently changed according to the composition
- $\text{ZrO}_2 - \text{SiO}_2 - \text{ZrO}_2$ Optic filters
- $\text{TiO}_2 - \text{CeO}_2$ Sensors
- $\text{SiO}_2 - \text{Me}_x\text{O}_y$ where Me –Cu, Ag, Co. Coloured layers, controlled release of bioactive ions
- $\text{TiO}_2 - \text{SiO}_2 - \text{TiO}_2$ Interference coloured layers

Inorganic-organic coatings, in systems.

- TEOS – trimetylchlórsilán (TMSCl) –IPA – H_2O – HNO_3
- TEOS – hexametyldisiloxán (HMDSO) –IPA – H_2O – HNO_3
- TEOS – amínopropyltrietyoxysilán (APTES) –IPA – H_2O – HNO_3
- TEOS – oktyltrietyoxysilán (OTES) –IPA – H_2O – HNO_3

where TEOS – tetraetoxysilan, IPA - izopropylalkohol

Inorganic – organic layers are applied as hydrophobic layers, protective layers that inhibit growth of biofilms, bactericide layers etc.

Keywords: coatings, sol-gel, oxidic coatings, inorganic-organic coatings.

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